

Development of a Microcontroller-based Measurement System for the Neuromuscular Blockade during Anesthesia

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Abstract

In medical surgery, anesthesiologists must keep track of a wide range of cardiac and respiratory parameters in addition to clinical indicators of ongoing anesthesia. For optimum surgical conditions, it is necessary to monitor neuromuscular blockades using diagnostic tools such as electromyograph (EMG), acceleromyograph (AMG), and mechanomyograph (MMG). Recently, short-acting drugs have become integral parts of modern anesthesia practice, which requires a real-time approach for measuring neuromuscular blockades, administering drugs, and controlling anesthesia. To achieve this goal, we have developed a microcontroller-based measurement system using an embedded Ethernet device called *Ethernut* containing an AVR-family microcontroller (ATmega128) and an Ethernet controller (LAN91C111). In this project, we have designed and built a new circuit board containing analog-to-digital converter (ADC) devices (MAX1270), which are connected to the expansion port of the Ethernut board. Our aim is to transmit ADC data via a local web server established on the Ethernut device using HTTP and TCP protocols with the help of an Ethernet controller. Our ADC board was designed and built using two 12-bit, 8-channel ADC MAX1270 devices, as well as op-amp buffers, digital isolators, an isolated DC/DC converter, and voltage regulators. The embedded Ethernet device, along with our ADC unit, provide us with a novel microcontroller-based measurement system. The main objective of the Ethernut-based data acquisition (DAQ) system is to retrieve data on neuromuscular blockades measured by various sensors (EMG, AMG, and MMG) from the MAX1270 integrated circuits (ICs) through the serial peripheral interface (SPI) port of the AVR microcontroller ATmega128. For our MAX1270-based ADC system, we developed a device driver program for working on Ethernut's real-time operating system *Nut/OS*, so it can in real time communicate with the ATmega128 microcon-

troller on the Ethernet board through the SPI port. We modified and tailored the HTTP server application of Nut/OS provided by egnite GmbH in order to establish a local HTTP/TCP server with the ADC device registered as a common gateway interface (CGI) on the Ethernet device for real-time data transmission over the Ethernet network to a desktop computer. We have programmed Ethernet's microcontroller to sample acquired data at 3 kHz and transmit it to its Ethernet-based real-time server in a standard format for data streams. A program like MATLAB on a desktop computer can retrieve and analyze the neuromuscular blockade data from this local server in order to monitor the status of a patient under anesthesia. The embedded DAQ system processes data from the neuromuscular sensors (EMG, AMG, and MMG) in a reliable way with a maximum bandwidth of about 400 Hz. Our results indicate that it can handle up to 1 kHz of data bandwidth. For higher data rates, the embedded device requires more memory space than is currently available. Therefore, this system is appropriate for processing sensor data with a moderate bandwidth. If we extend and improve our embedded Ethernet measurement system, it can be used for a number of practical applications in anesthesia clinics that require accurate observations of patient behavior. This microcontroller-based system is easily extensible and can be used as a controller for other automation applications.

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Contents

Abstract	vi
Contents	xi
List of Figures	xiv
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Measurements of Neuromuscular Blockades	2
1.1.1 Electromyography	2
1.1.2 Acceleromyography	4
1.1.3 Mechanomyography	4
1.2 Monitor and Control of Anesthesia	5
1.3 Thesis Outline	7
2 Data Acquisition System	9
2.1 Special Requirements	10
2.1.1 Analog to Digital Converter	11
2.1.2 Mapping Analog to Digital	15
2.1.3 Standard Peripheral Ports	21
2.2 Design and Development	26
2.2.1 Hardware Capabilities of Ethernut	26
2.2.2 Software Facilities of Nut/OS	30
3 Analog-to-Digital Converter System	31
3.1 Overview of the ADC Circuit	33

CONTENTS

3.1.1	MAX1270: 12-bit ADC Device	33
3.1.2	LT1079: Op-Amp Buffers	35
3.1.3	ADuM1201/2401: Digital Isolators	36
3.1.4	TEL 3-1223: DC-to-DC Converter	37
3.2	Communication with Ethernet-based DAQ	38
4	Nut/OS and ADC Device Driver	41
4.1	Nut/OS: Ethernet Real-time Operating System	41
4.1.1	Kernel API Functions	42
4.1.2	Network API Functions	49
4.2	MAX1270 ADC Device Driver	55
4.2.1	SPI API Functions	56
4.2.2	ADC API Functions	59
4.2.3	Delay API Functions	61
4.3	Tailored HTTP Server Application	62
4.3.1	Initialization in Main Thread	63
4.3.2	Configuration in HTTP Service Thread	63
4.3.3	ADC Communication	64
4.4	MATLAB Program	66
5	Conclusions	71
	References	74
A	Schematic Circuit Diagram	79
B	Printed Circuit Board	83
C	Data Sheet	87
D	Glossary	89

E	Supplementary Material	91
E.1	Installation and Configuration	92
E.2	Tailored HTTP Server Program	97
E.3	MAX1270 Device Driver	108
E.4	MATLAB Code	113
E.5	Default ROM Program	114
E.6	Compiler Makefile	115

CONTENTS

List of Figures

1.1	Acceleromyographs, electromyographs, and mechanomyographs.	3
1.2	A view of the Rostock Assistant System for Anesthesia Control. . .	6
2.1	The effective range of digital data made from analogs.	11
2.2	ADC with whitening and dewhitening filters.	12
2.3	Sampling restriction on signals.	13
2.4	Aliasing of signals after analog-to-digital conversion.	14
2.5	Mapping continuous signals to discrete signals	16
2.6	Mapping discrete signals to zero-order hold signals.	19
2.7	Analog-to-digital converter with track/hold units.	20
2.8	Analog-to-digital converter with different peripheral ports.	22
2.9	Serial peripheral interface ports with different modes.	23
2.10	An example of I ² C communication.	25
2.11	A schematic view of the Ethernut system.	27
3.1	A typical operating circuit for MAX1270.	34
3.2	A diagram of buffers in LT1079	35
3.3	Functional block diagrams of ADuM1201 and ADuM2401	36
3.4	Diagrams of DC-to-DC converters with single and dual outputs. . .	37
3.5	Transmissions between the sensors, ADC, Ethernut, and PC.	38
3.6	An operating circuit for ATmega128.	39
4.1	Serial Peripheral Interface Bus	56

LIST OF FIGURES

4.2	Diagram of communication between Nut/OS and MATLAB.	68
4.3	Data acquired by the ADC system and transferred via Ethernet.	69
A.1	The Schematic Circuit Diagram of our ADC System.	82
B.1	The Printed Circuit Board of our ADC System.	84
C.1	MAX1270/MAX1271 Programmable Register	88

1

Introduction

When performing a clinical surgery, anesthesiologists are required to monitor and control a set of hemodynamic and respiratory variables, in addition to clinical indicators for proper hypnosis and analgesia. A continuous neuromuscular block is required in neurosurgery, thoracic surgery, and abdominal surgery in order to ensure the best possible conditions for surgical operations. Contemporary anesthesia practice incorporates an increasing number of modern drugs with shorter durations of action. This necessitates the use of a continuous mode for the drug application and suggests the use of automatic control. A practice that enables controlling the infusion pump is necessary for building a closed-loop control system. One of the problems that stands in the way of the development, such as a control system, is overcome with the invention of remote-controlled infusion pumps.

From a control engineering point of view, the challenges of giving the right anesthesia can be seen as problems with multiple inputs and several outputs (see, e.g. [1]). Anesthetists should decide how much medicine a patient needs by looking at the dosing regimes prescribed by the drug manufacturer, which are typically based on the patient's body weight. Physicians who have more expertise are better able to correlate the dosing regimen with their observations of the patient's general behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

The monitoring of the patient's level of muscle relaxation presents another challenge to the anesthetist in the operating room. Electromyography (EMG), acceleromyography (AMG), and mechanomyography (MMG) are the three techniques that can be used to record the muscle response occurring after stimulation of a muscle's respective motor nerve. AMG is currently largely acknowledged as the method of choice for measuring muscle force (see [2]). However, MMG is currently utilized for scientific purposes in neuromuscular monitoring, which is not currently suitable in ordinary clinical practice.

The anesthesiologist may administer extra dose injections of muscle relaxants to keep the patient relaxed, depending on the measurement of neuromuscular blockages. Because of the development of new drugs with short to ultra-short action times, injection intervals have become incredibly small. Therefore, a control system for the continuous drug administration is required, as neuromuscular blockages are constantly monitored while anesthetic and surgery are being performed.

1.1 Measurements of Neuromuscular Blockades

1.1.1 Electromyography

Electromyography (EMG) is a diagnostic method that measures how muscles react at rest and when they are contracting and relaxing. It is performed using an electromyograph sensor to record electromyographic signals. In this procedure, a thin needle electrode is inserted into the muscle. During contraction and relaxation, the electrode detects the electrical signals generated by the muscle. Evaluation of the strength and function of individual muscles or groups of muscles can be accomplished through the use of an electromyograph. In cases of neurological disorders such as carpal tunnel syndrome or peripheral neuropathy, it may also be used to pinpoint the exact location of the nerve injury.

1.1. MEASUREMENTS OF NEUROMUSCULAR BLOCKADES

Figure 1.1: Top Image: Acceleromyographs and electromyographs, which are attached to the body, measure neuromuscular blockades [1]. Bottom Images: electromyography and acceleromyography sensors (left) and mechanomyography sensor (right) connected to hands [3].

Electromyographic signals should be amplified, so they can be displayed in a graphical user interface on a desktop computer. Electromyograph provides efficient information on neuromuscular activity for human-machine interfaces (HMI) [4], which may also be employed for helping people with physical disabilities and those with neuromuscular impairments. To recognize certain patterns in electromyographic signals, several methods, including statistical approaches and neural networks, have been developed. Recent improvements to probabilistic neural networks (PNN) have given us a way to recognize patterns in EMG data [5]. Integrating statistical models into the design of PNNs as prior knowledge can lead to remarkable achievements. PNNs have been studied as a

1. INTRODUCTION

key tool for recognizing the pattern in EMG signals (see, e.g. [4, 5]).

1.1.2 Acceleromyography

Acceleromyography (AMG) is a method of neuromuscular monitoring used to see how a muscle reacts when a nerve is stimulated. During anesthesia, acceleromyograph is often used to track how muscle relaxants happen and to control how drugs are administered during anesthesia. An AMG approach involves putting an electrode on the muscle, most often the adductor pollicis muscle in the hand (see Fig. 1.1). The muscle is then contracted using a nerve stimulator, which sends an electrical current to the nerve and causes the muscle to tighten. An accelerometer connected to the electrode measures the contraction and provides a quantitative measurement of the force contracting the muscle.

Most of the time, the result of AMG measurements is shown as a percentage of the twitch response compared to the baseline in a monitoring application program on a computer. The twitch response is the first muscle contraction that happens prior to the delivery of drugs, such as mivacurium, propofol and remifentanyl. Anesthesiologists should be able to monitor neuromuscular blockade data, so they can adjust the dose of drugs in accordance with it. This may be accomplished by measuring the reaction of the muscle to a nerve stimulation using an embedded measurement system connected to a user-interface monitoring system such as a desktop computer (see Fig. 1.2).

1.1.3 Mechanomyography

Mechanomyography (MMG) is a method for neuromuscular observations that measures the mechanical vibrations caused by muscle contractions. It is a non-intrusive technique that is employed to quantify the muscle's activities in some applications, such as sports and research. In this method, an accelerometer or vibration sensor is attached to the surface skin of the muscle (see Fig. 1.1). As

the muscle contracts, it generates mechanical vibrations that can be measured using the MMG sensor. This signal can then be analyzed to quantify the muscle contraction.

Mechanomyograph may be employed in the assessment of the muscular function, the monitoring of anesthesia, and the administration of drug delivery. Since MMG is still a fairly new technique, more research needs to be done to see if it can be used for anesthesia monitoring. It is still being studied to be considered as a clinical tool for assessing the function of muscles in anesthesia and other applications.

1.2 Monitor and Control of Anesthesia

In a surgery, anesthesiologists look at a number of different signs, like the EEG, to find the level of anesthesia. Measurable outputs are necessary for the automated administration of drugs. There is currently no way to directly control the drug delivery during anesthesia. It is anticipated that the EEG signals will allow us to monitor and control the depth of anesthesia. Uncertainties in the anesthesia depth may also be obtained from the EEG data using a statistical algorithm. However, variations in EEG signals with different anesthetic drugs could be the main disadvantage in the use of the EEG indicators.

In the case of neuromuscular blockades, there are two components that make up the controller of a patient: the medicine application system and measurement system as shown in Figure 1.2.. For example, the liquid anesthetic Propofol and a bispectral index (BIS) monitor for data collection have been used in some studies (see [6, 7] for some details). At the moment, there are two different ways to give anesthetic drugs: with an infusion pump or with an infusion pump coupled with a drug distributor system. In both open loop control and closed loop control studies, target-controlled infusion systems have been employed [6, 7]. With the help of a target blood level, the target-controlled

1. INTRODUCTION

Figure 1.2: A schematic view of the instruments used for the development of automatic drug delivery by the Rostock Assistant System for Anesthesia Control [2] (for details see [6, 7]).

infusion system can decide the required infusion rate. The controller first calculates and then projects the infusion rate. Some requirements for the patient must be considered by the controller of anesthetic depth. There are different approaches to achieving this objective: the development of an anesthetic controller or a predictive controller. A robust control approach also seems to be the best option when a reliable model is unavailable. A fuzzy control system can be built without the use of any numerical technique, and they can offer us a robust controller.

A high-quality measurement of neuromuscular signals is a requirement for developing a closed loop system in an anesthesia control system. In this project, we therefore aim to develop a new measurement device for simultaneously recording the relaxation state recorded with EMG, MMG, and AMG sensors.

While different peripheral devices are employed to stimulate a muscular motor nerve, the electromyograph measures the electrical signal generated by the muscle action. Moreover, the mechanomyograph can also detect the force produced by the thumb following stimulation. Additionally, the acceleromyograph is able to measure the acceleration of the thumb in response to stimulation. Our measurement system should be able to measure the EMG, MMG, and AMG signals with high accuracy. A suggested piece of hardware equipment shown in Figure 1.2 could be employed to monitor and control anesthesia in clinical practice. High quality measured data provided by the measurement device is vital, just as the controlled infusion pump and anesthesiologist are important.

For accurate measurements of neuromuscular blockades, we need a data acquisition system with an analog-to-digital converter unit to collect analog signals from the MMG, EMG, and AMG sensors and transfer them into a local network. The controller system can then use the information from the data acquisition system to control anesthesia. Because the process is different for each patient, the patient-centered controller must be developed to prevent any mistakes during the surgery. For a proper control of anesthesia, the level of anesthesia needs to be carefully monitored, because cross-reactions are not small (see [1] for more information). This can be achieved with a data acquisition system that perfectly fulfills the required conditions in clinical practice.

1.3 Thesis Outline

The aim of this project is to develop a measuring system using a microcontroller-based device equipped with an Ethernet peripheral component to collect data on neuromuscular blockades or the purpose of monitoring and controlling anesthesia. In Chapter 2, we describe a data acquisition system (DAQ) designed and developed using the embedded Ethernet board sold by egnite GmbH. Chapter 3 describes a new analog-to-digital converter (ADC) system we built using the

1. INTRODUCTION

ADC device MAX1270 as well as an overview of other electronic elements we used on our ADC board. We briefly provide overviews of the microcontroller ATmega128 and Ethernet device LAN91C111 on the Ethernet board that we employed as our DAQ system to collect data from the ADC unit and transfer it into a local web server established on Ethernet for the use by a computer. Chapter 4 explains how we configured the real-time operating system Nut/OS of the Ethernet Board for communication with the ADC and the data transition into the Ethernet network. In particular, we have developed a device driver program for our MAX1270-based ADC system to work on the real-time operating system Nut/OS of the Ethernet board, and also tailored the HTTP server application of Nut/OS to register our ADC system as a common gateway interface (CGI) for transmitting data via HTTP and TCP to a program in MATLAB. Finally, our results and limitations are discussed and concluded in Chapter 5.

2

Data Acquisition System

To monitor anesthesia, neuromuscular blockades need to be accumulated over long periods of time, preferably with as few breaks as possible, so that a pattern in the signals is recognizable. For example, they could be continuous signals with an extremely low signal-to-noise ratio. To distinguish the signal from the background noise, the signal must first be recorded over a considerable amount of time. Moreover, it is desirable that neuromuscular blockade detectors have a very low downtime, allowing for the identification of single events. The detection of such a signal needs to go through a process called synchronicity analysis, which involves verifying that more than one detector measures the same properties of a signal, such as arrival time and amplitude. Afterward, the detection can be considered credible. It is required that the measurement of each individual detector have a long time duration in order to provide a significant temporal overlap between the data segments coming from different detectors. In terms of analyzing the neuromuscular blockade data, it is obvious that there is a requirement for a long duty cycle.

Every neuromuscular blockade needs a robust and reliable data acquisition system (DAQ) that can acquire data continuously over several seconds. The neuromuscular output signal contains the EMG, MMG, and AMG information. For them at least 8 channels are recorded that are required for monitoring and

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

detecting. The DAQ digitizes all these analog voltage signals and stores them in a standardized format. In this chapter the requirements and the design of the DAQ is explained in detail.

The measurement of neuromuscular blockades needs a data acquisition system (DAQ) that is robust and reliable for collecting continuous analog data over a few seconds. The analog neuromuscular data on EMG, MMG, and AMG are all converted into digital outputs. At least eight channels on the DAQ required for monitoring and detection are captured during the recording process. All of these analog voltage signals are digitized by the DAQ, and then they are stored in a user-defined standardized format for the transmission into a ethernet network. This chapter provides a detailed description of the development of a DAQ designed for measuring neuromuscular blockades in this project.

2.1 Special Requirements

A DAQ suitable for the purpose of our anesthesia monitoring in the project needs to fulfill a number of special requirements, all of which are discussed in the following subsections. The first prerequisite that needs to be met is that the quantization noise introduced by the process of converting analog signals to digital ones does not limit the overall quality of the resulting quantized data. The quantization noise caused by the analog-to-digital conversion must be reduced to a negligible level in the digital band. For example, if analog data are sampled by the DAQ at a rate of about 110 kbps, every component of the DAQ system is required to operate at a higher speed such as 1 Mbps that is sufficient to handle a continuous data streaming at that sampling rate. Moreover, the converted sampling data must have high digital quantities (e.g., 12 bits) that is accurate enough to a high degree for recognizing the pattern in analog signals. To reduce the amount of downtime on the analog-to-digital converter, the used microchip hardware must have a high degree of reliability under different clin-

Figure 2.1: The effective frequency range of digital data made from analog signals limited by the quantization noise of the analog-to-digital converter.

ical conditions. The next subsections provide more in-depth details on these specific requirements, which have been considered for the development of our DAQ system.

2.1.1 Analog to Digital Converter

An analog-to-digital converter (ADC) is necessary to convert the analog signals produced by the neuromuscular blockade sensors into a digital form that can be sent to and stored in a computer. The process of analog-to-digital conversion quantizes the signal in both amplitude and time in such a way that the digital signal is represented by the amplitude levels that are made from a finite set of 2^n digital quantities, where n is the number of bits used by the ADC, so called the *sampling resolution*. The amplitudes are expressed using discrete time intervals $m \times t_s$, where m is an arbitrary integer number and t_s is the *sample time* of the ADC. The quantization of the analog amplitudes introduces the quantization noise, leading to a limitation on the resulting digital data (see Fig. 2.1). The quantization of the time also limits the bandwidth of the converted signal. Therefore, we need to carefully choose the sampling resolution n and the sam-

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

Figure 2.2: Analog-to-digital converter with a whitening and dewhitening filtering technique for reducing the quantization noise.

pling time t_s in such a way that the sensitivity of our DAQ system in terms of amplitude levels and time intervals is not restricted by the quantization noise.

Quantization Noise

The quantization noise shows up in the quantized data because the analog amplitude is rounded up to the next discretized level (see [8] for more details). This is based on two parameters of the ADC: sampling resolution (n) and effective frequency range (f_{eff}). The effective frequency range (f_{eff}), which is a function of the ADC sampling time (t_s), implies an amplitude effective level U_{eff} . The voltage amplitude U_{LSB} of the least significant bit (LSB) is expressed using the sampling resolution and amplitude effective level as follows: $U_{\text{LSB}} = U_{\text{eff}}/2^n$. The amplitude density of the introduced quantization noise is then defined by $U_{\text{QN}} = U_{\text{LSB}}/\sqrt{6f_s}$, where f_s is the sampling frequency. To accurately measure an analog signal, the analog voltage amplitude should be above the quantization noise level U_{QN} at all the frequencies.

Fig. 2.1 shows the effective frequency range (dash-dotted line) of an ADC system limited by the quantization noise (dotted line), which restricts the accuracy of the analog signal (solid line) measured by the ADC. In this example, the measurement of digital signals is limited by the quantization noise to frequencies below 1 kHz. Fig. 2.2 illustrates a whitening and dewhitening filtering

Figure 2.3: Sampling restriction on a sinusoidal signal with a frequency of $0.2f_s$ (solid line) below the Nyquist frequency ($f_N = f_s/2$) that is indistinguishable from a sinusoidal signal with a frequency of $1.2f_s$ (dashed line) for an analog-to-digital converter with a sampling frequency of f_s .

technique used by some DAQ systems for reducing the quantization noise. In this approach, analog signals that have different strengths at different frequencies are *whitened* before they go to the ADC, which makes the strengths at all frequencies the same. After the ADC conversion, the digital signals are again transferred to correct discretization levels by reversing the whitening process through the *dewhitening* filter. For our DAQ system, we use an ADC microchip (MAX1270, see Chapter 3) with a sampling resolution of 12 bits, which leads to a quantization noise of $\sim 8 \mu\text{V}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ over the voltage range of $\pm 5 \text{V}$. The sampling resolution of 12 bits is large enough that the whitening and dewhitening filters are not necessary for our DAQ system for the purpose of anesthesia monitoring.

Sampling Rate and Aliasing

Sampling continuous signals at a sampling frequency rate of $f_s = (t_s)^{-1}$ restricts the bandwidth of the converted signal to $f_N = f_s/2$ the so-called Nyquist fre-

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

Figure 2.4: Aliasing of analog signals (dashed line) at $f, f + f_s, f + 2f_s, \dots$ results in a digital signal (solid line) after the analog-to-digital conversion with the sampling frequency rate of f_s .

quency. At the sampling intervals $t_s = n/f_s$, the signal S_1 with a frequency of $f_1 < f_N$ cannot be distinguished from the signal S_2 with the same amplitude at a frequency of $f_2 = f_1 + mf_s$, where m is an arbitrary integer number. This can be described using mathematical formulas using the fact that $\exp(i2\pi f_s(nm)/(f_s)) = 1$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_1(t_s) &= S \exp(i2\pi f_1 t_s) \times 1 = S \exp(i2\pi f_1 t_s) \exp\left(i2\pi f_s \frac{n}{f_s} m\right) \\
 &= S \exp(i2\pi f_1 t_s) \exp(i2\pi f_s t_s m) = S \exp(i2\pi (f_1 + mf_s) t_s) \\
 &= S \exp(i2\pi f_2 t_s) = S_2(t_s).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

This restriction is illustrated in Fig. 2.3 using two signals at $0.2f_s$ and $1.2f_s$. Hence, different analog signals at frequencies $f, f + f_s, f + 2f_s, \dots$ are indistinguishable during sampling, which is called *aliasing*. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 2.4. The dashed curves describe the central frequencies of different analog signals shifted by the sampling frequency rate of f_s . The solid curve represents their resulting digital signal following an analog-to-digital conversion

To prevent aliasing, signals at frequencies higher than the Nyquist frequency ($f_N = f_s/2$) need to be attenuated by a low-pass filter, so called the anti-aliasing filter. For the DAQ system with a sampling frequency of $f_s = 4$ kHz, the effective bandwidth may be extended from the Nyquist frequency of $f_N = 2$ kHz to about 7 kHz due if a suitable anti-aliasing filter is used. However, the integrated circuit (MAX1270; see Chapter 3) we chose for our DAQ system works at a bandwidth of 5 MHz, which is much higher than the neuromuscular blockade signals with typical bandwidths of around 2 kHz. This is sufficiently high for sampling the neuromuscular blockade without the need for an anti-aliasing filter.

2.1.2 Mapping Analog to Digital

The analog signals $x(t)$ from a continuous space are mapped to the digital data $x[t]$ in a discrete space using a ADC unit as seen in Fig. 2.5: $x(t) \xrightarrow{\text{ADC}} x[t]$. The resolution of the resulting digital signals depends on the number of bits used by the ADC unit. For example, an ADC microchip with $n = 8$ bits can discrete an analog input into $2^n - 1 = 255$ discretized levels or in order words from 0 to 255.¹ An ADC system can be categorized as either linear or nonlinear. In a linear ADC system, the range of input analog signals are linearly proportional to the output digital data. However, a non-linear ADC system leads to digital signals with varying discretized levels. The quantization noise introduced by a ADC unit and other synchronization-related faults during the conversation could have a non-linear nature.

When a continuous signal is mixed with a digital signal, the reconstruction of an analog signal from discrete samples could be challenging. The Fourier Transform (FT) could be a suitable approach for analyzing this reconstruction issue, as it is able to describe both continuous and discrete signals in the fre-

¹The amplitude resolution R of the discrete signal is equal to the measurement range E of the analog signal divided by the number of discretized levels as $R = \frac{E}{2^n - 1}$, where n is the number of bits used for discretization.

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

Figure 2.5: Mapping (a) continuous signals to (b) discrete signals [9].

quency domain. However, the ideal technique for reconstructing analog from digital is not easily implementable in any realistic system. For example, if we sample a sinusoidal signal at sampling intervals, the sampled signal looks discrete, so we are not able to distinguish whether the original signal was discrete or sinusoidal. We should note that the sampler provides no information regarding the behavior of the signal between sampling intervals. This requires us to impose some constraints on the analog signal. In theory, it makes sense to require that the signal be sampled smoothly at a higher sampling rate. This can be implemented by selecting the frequency rate of the sampling, which is equal to or higher than the highest frequency present in the signal. Alternatively, a smoothing low-pass filter can be used to restrict the bandwidth of the analog signal before the ADC unit, which may solve the reconstruction problem.

Sampling Theorem

The quantization of a continuous signal in a discrete space produces the quantized signal. The quantization is performed by continuously sampling in equal

time intervals, which should satisfy the “Nyquist–Shannon sampling theorem”² to correctly reconstruct the signal in a discrete space. According to the sampling theorem (see, e.g., [9]), “the continuous signal is correctly mapped onto the discrete space if it is band-limited and the sampling frequency is higher than twice the signal bandwidth.” Thus, the necessary condition for a correct reconstruction of the signal with a signal bandwidth of B is to use a sampling frequency f_s with $f_s > 2B$. The sampling of an analog signal is performed by periodic signals with t_s units of time, which is called the sampling interval. This results in a sequence of numbers called samples. Each sample corresponds to a specific time when it was recorded with a sampling frequency of $f_s = 1/t_s$. The minimum sampling frequency is $2B$, which is usually called the *Nyquist rate*. It is also worthwhile mentioning the *Nyquist frequency* ($\frac{1}{2}f_s$), which is half the sampling frequency, is the highest frequency that can be reliably measured.

The sampling theorem says how frequently a signal needs to be sampled for the samples to be an accurate representation of a continuous signal. Let us again consider the issue associated with the reconstruction of the analog signal from the discrete samples. This issue is easily solvable in the frequency domain using the Fourier transform (see, e.g. [10] for details). Assume the Fourier transform $x(t) \xrightarrow{\text{FT}} X(jf)$, where $x(t)$ and $X(jf)$ are the signal in the time-domain and frequency-domain, respectively, then the Fourier transformation (FT) for the resulting sampled signal is as follows [10]

$$X_\delta(jf) = \frac{1}{t_s} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} X(jf - jkf_s), \quad (2.2)$$

where $X(jf)$ and $X_\delta(jf)$ are the analog signal and the resulting digital signal in the frequency-domain, respectively, and $j \equiv \sqrt{-1}$ is the imaginary unit.³

To correctly restore the analog signal $X(jf)$, we need to apply the recon-

²Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem is also known as Nyquist-Shannon-Kotelnikov, Whittaker-Shannon-Kotelnikov, and Whittaker-Nyquist-Kotelnikov-Shannon theorem.

³In physics and mathematics, the imaginary unit is shown as $i \equiv \sqrt{-1}$.

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

struction operator $H_r(jf)$ to the digital one $X_\delta(jf)$:

$$X(jf) = X_\delta(jf)H_r(jf), \quad (2.3)$$

which removes all the replicates of $X_\delta(jf)$ emerging at kf_s . The reconstruction operator is defined as:

$$H_r(jf) = \begin{cases} t_s, & |f| < f_s/2 \\ 0, & |f| > f_s/2 \end{cases}. \quad (2.4)$$

Transforming the operation (2.3) in the frequency domain to the time domain yields

$$x(t) = x_\delta(t) * h_r(t), \quad (2.5)$$

where $h_r(t)$ is the reconstruction operator in the time domain mapped using the Fourier transform $h_r(t) \xleftrightarrow{\text{FT}} H_r(j\omega)$, and $x_\delta(t)$ is the reconstructed discrete signals in the time domain defined as:

$$x_\delta(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} x[n] \delta(t - nt_s). \quad (2.6)$$

Substituting Eq. (2.6) into Eq. (2.5) yields:

$$x(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} x[n] h_r(t - nt_s). \quad (2.7)$$

Using the time-domain reconstruction operator defined using the normalized sinc function as

$$h_r(t) \equiv \text{sinc}(f_s t) \equiv \frac{\sin(\pi f_s t)}{\pi f_s t}, \quad (2.8)$$

leads to

$$x(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} x[n] \text{sinc}(f_s(t - nt_s)), \quad (2.9)$$

commonly known as the *theory of ideal band-limited interpolation* (see, e.g. [10]), which describes how to correctly interpolate to reproduce a continuous signal from discrete samples of a band-limited signal. In practice we cannot implement Eq. (2.9). First of all, it is a non-causal system, meaning that the

Figure 2.6: Mapping (a) discrete signals to (b) zero-order hold signals [9].

output $x(t)$ depends on the values of the input $x[n]$ in the past and in the future. Second, the effect of each sample spreads across an infinite amount of time due to the time duration in $h_r(t)$. A practical reconstruction of continuous signals is implementable with a method known as *zero-order hold*, which we discuss in the next subsection.

Zero-Order Hold

The zero-order hold is a signal reconstruction operator which simply holds the value $x[n]$ for t_s . This leads to discrete stair-steps in $x_0(t)$ with intervals of t_s , which are approximately associated with the continuous one (see Fig. 2.6). The zero-order hold is mathematically described by a sum of rectangular pulses shifted by the sampling intervals. Let us consider the mathematical model of a zero-order hold defined as

$$h_0(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 < t < t_s \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (2.10)$$

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

Figure 2.7: Analog-to-digital converter with: (a) multiplexed track/hold amplifier, which uses one track/hold unit for all channels (AD7994 [11]); and (b) simultaneous sampling technique, which uses one track/hold unit per channel (AD7874 [12]).

The output of the zero-order hold can be expressed in term of $h_0(t)$ as follows:

$$x_0(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} x[n]h_0(t - nt_s). \quad (2.11)$$

Applying the Fourier transform to Eq. (2.11) yields

$$X_0(jf) = X_\delta(jf)H_0(jf), \quad (2.12)$$

where $H_0(jf)$ is the zero-order hold in the frequency domain mapped using the Fourier transform $h_0(t) \xleftrightarrow{\text{FT}} H_0(jf) = e^{-j\pi f t_s} \text{sinc}(f t_s)$, where $\text{sinc}(x) \equiv \sin(\pi x)/(\pi x)$ is the normalized sinc function

Sampling and Holding

In order to convert an analog signal into a digital one, a special device is used to hold the analog signal while the sampling operation is done. This device is called the *sample and hold unit*, which is employed when several analog signals simultaneously need to be measured. Each signal is sampled and held using a common sampling clock, and then they are synchronously readable.

One sample-and-hold unit can be shared by several channels, making it a low-cost device that can be used for some commercial purposes (see Fig. 2.7 a). However, preserving the relative phase of the multiple signals is not possible if

all the channels share a single sample and hold unit. In some applications, such as AC motor controllers, where the relative phase is important, one sample and hold unit is necessary for each channel (see Fig. 2.7 b). This makes it possible to collect several sampling signals at the same time without any phase errors between signals that are connected to multiple sensors.

2.1.3 Standard Peripheral Ports

The right standard peripheral protocol should be chosen for the transmission of sampled sensor data of neuromuscular blockades over a communication port. A standard protocol for digital communication should have different features that ensure the integrity and reliability of data exchange over a single or multiple channels. The standard peripheral protocol for transmitting the sensor data from our ADC unit to the DAQ system must adhere to certain principles so that the anesthesia monitoring system can function correctly. In this section, we introduce three common standards used for peripherals: parallel, SPI, and I²C (see Fig. 2.8). Among them, the SPI protocol is appropriate for our DAQ system owing to its high speed and reliability over long distances.

Parallel Interface Bus

The parallel interface transfers many bits of information simultaneously through a transmission port (see Fig. 2.8 a). The number of bits transferred at once multiplied by the bit rate of each individual path determines the speed of a parallel port. Although a parallel peripheral bus is the simplest method, it has some limitations due to the limited length of a parallel cable. At the physical layer, the difference between a parallel and serial port channel is the number of different wires or strands utilized for simultaneous transmission between two devices. However, parallel ports have been abandoned in favor of serial ports due to the falling cost of microchips and the increased demand for high speed and longer

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

Figure 2.8: Analog-to-digital converter with three different peripheral ports, namely (a) parallel (AD7874 [12]), (b) SPI (AD7924 [13]), and (c) I²C (AD7994 [11]).

cable length.

Serial Peripheral Interface Bus

The Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) bus enables synchronous, serial, duplex transmission between the a microcontroller device and peripheral devices in master or slave mode using only the four pins (see Fig. 2.8 b). The SPI bus can function with one master device and any number of slave devices (see Fig. 2.9). Activating the SPI enable (SPE) bit in the SPI Control Register 1 (SPICR1) enables the SPI system. While the SPE bit is enabled, the four SPI port pins are used for the SPI transmission (see, e.g. [14]), namely MOSI, MISO, \overline{SS} , and

Figure 2.9: Serial peripheral interface ports with two different communication modes: (a) one master and one slave; and (b) one master and multiple slaves.

SCLK (see Fig. 2.9 a), described in details below:

- Master Out/Slave In (MOSI) pin transmits data out from the SPI module in master mode configuration and receives data in slave mode.
- Master In/Slave Out (MISO) pin is used to transmit data out from the SPI module in slave mode and to receive data in master mode.
- Slave Select (\overline{SS}) pin is employed to send the select signal from the SPI module to another SPI peripheral device in master mode and is used to receive the select signal in slave mode (see Fig. 2.9 b).
- Serial Clock (SCLK) pin outputs the clock signal in the master configuration or receives the clock signal in slave mode.

The SPI module operates in three different modes, namely run, wait, and stop (see, e.g. [14]), described in details below:

- Run mode is the basic mode for operation.

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

- Wait mode is used to put the SPI operation a configurable low power state, which can be controlled by the SPI Stop in Wait Mode (SPISWAI) bit in the SPI Control Register 2 (SPICR2). In wait mode, the SPI operates similar to run mode when the SPISWAI bit is deactivated. If the SPISWAI bit is activated, the SPI moves to a power conservative state in which the SPI clock generator is off. In master mode, transmission in progress halts in wait mode, but is restores as soon as returning to run mode. In slave mode, data receiving and transmitting continues in such a way that the slave remains synchronized to the master device.
- Stop mode puts the SPI model in an inactive state to reduce the power consumption. In master mode, transmission in progress halts in stop mode, but is restores as soon as returning to run mode. In slave mode, data receiving and transmitting continues in such a way that the slave device maintains synchronization to the master device.

The SPI Data Register is the primary part of the SPI module. The MOSI and MISO pins connect the master's and the slave's 8-bit data registers to make a 16-bit distributed register. During a data transmission, the serial clock from the master device serially shifts this 16-bit register by eight bits, allowing data to travel between the master device and the slave device. After a transmission is done, the data that were written to the master SPI Data Register are sent to the slave device, whereas the data that were read from the master SPI Data Register are received by the slave device.

Inter-Integrated Circuit

Inter-Integrated Circuit (I²C) serial bus is a packet-switched, single-ended, serial communication protocol that allows a microcontroller-based system to quickly collect data from lower-speed peripheral integrated circuits (ICs) over a short distance. In addition, because ICs are directly attached to the I²C bus without

Figure 2.10: An example of I²C communication used in a high-performance, highly integrated TV system [15].

the need for any external interface, a prototype device can be updated by simply attaching or detaching ICs to or from the I²C bus. This standard has only two bidirectional open-drain lines, namely serial data (SDA) and serial clock (SCL) (see Fig. 2.8 c). The simple 2-wire serial bus simplifies interconnections, resulting in ICs with fewer pins and fewer conductive traces and vias on a printed circuit board (PCB), resulting in a smaller, less expensive PCB.

Two wires, serial data (SDA) and serial clock (SCL), transmit data between the connected devices (see, e.g., Fig. 2.10). Each device has its own unique address and, depending on its role, can act as either a sender or a receiver. In data transmissions, equipment can also be configured in master or slave mode in addition to sender or receiver mode. In master mode, the device sends data to the bus and creates the necessary clock signals for data transmission. At that point, any addressed device is configured as a slave.

Although the I²C protocol allows us to have a smaller, inexpensive PCB, its

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

low efficiency over long distances and low speeds make it a poor choice for our DAQ system. Thus, we chose the SPI communication standard for our DAQ system and ADC unit, and we searched for a DAQ system (Ethernut broad v2.1), discussed in the following section, as well as an ADC IC equipped with the SPI port (MAX1270 ADC chipset discussed in Chapter 3).

2.2 Design and Development

To build our microcontroller-based measurement system for anesthesia monitoring with the special requirements discussed in the previous section, we base our DAQ system on the hardware of the *Ethernut*⁴ board version 2.1 [16], equipped with a real-time operating system (Nut/OS), built by egnite GmbH.⁵ The development was carried out with the assistance of the same hardware components available on the Ethernut board and works with an open-source real-time operating system (OS) called *NUT/OS*. However, we design and build an ADC circuit to work with this DAQ system, which is discussed in Chapter 3, and we develop a device driver program for this ADC unit for functioning in NUT/OS (see Chapter 4). In the following text, we introduce the hardware and software features of the Ethernut board.

2.2.1 Hardware Capabilities of Ethernut

The Ethernut board can be utilized for a variety of novel applications. With the available hardware, software, and tools, we can economically develop various controller systems for different purposes. The board is suitable for many innovative products in automation and control. Some applications made by the Ethernut board includes: remote diagnostic, networked monitoring system, and industrial embedded Ethernet devices [16].

⁴<http://www.ethernut.de>

⁵<http://www.egnite.de>

Figure 2.11: A schematic view of the Ethernut system version 2.1 [16].

For the development of our DAQ system, we use the Ethernut system version 2.1 [16], which has an Atmel AVR-family microcontroller ATmega128 made with advanced reduced instruction set computer (RISC) architecture and a Microchip LAN91C111 Ethernet controller with Medium Access Control (MAC) layer and Physical Layer (PHY) integrated circuits. The main components on the Ethernut system are (see Fig. 2.11):

- ATmega128: 8-bit RISC microcontroller with 128kB in-system programmable Flash ROM, 4Kb Internal SRAM, and 4Kb programmable EEPROM, equipped with eight 10-bit ADC channels, two 8-bit and two 16-bit timer/counters, and programmable watchdog timer,
- LAN91C111: 10/100 Mbps Ethernet controller with fully integrate IEEE 802.3 MAC+PHY connected to the LAN transformer chipset TG110,
- ST3222 and ST483 Serials: RS-232 controlled by the STMicroelectronics IC ST3222 and low-speed RS-485 controlled by the IC ST483,
- AT45DB041 Flash: 512 kB SPI data flash (AT45DB041),

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

- K6T4008 SRAM: 32 kB static random-access memory (SRAM) and 480 kB banked SRAM (K6T4008) managed by a Xilinx Complex Programmable Logic Device (CPLD) XC9535XL programmed by egnite GmbH,
- LM3940 and LM1086: low dropout voltage regulators of 5 and 3.3 V.

ATmega128 microcontroller is undoubtedly the most vital component on the Ethernut board. It is described in details by the ATmega128 datasheet published by Atmel [17]. There is a 64-pin expansion port on the Ethernut system, which can be used to attach external devices such as a ADC system. We connect our designed ADC system (described in Chapter 3) to this 64-pin port. Two Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter (UART) channels are provided by the microcontroller and connected to the device ST3222 for supporting an RS-232 channel and the device ST483 for an RS-485 port. A Xilinx CPLD is utilized to control the memory selection on the external SRAM K6T4008 and to manage the LAN Controller LAN91C111. Uploading programs into the microcontroller ATmega128 is done through a Joint Test Action Group (JTAG) port.

Peripheral Ports

The Ethernut board has three peripheral ports: two serial ports, one Ethernet, and one 64-pin expansion port. It has both an RS-232 serial communication terminal and an RS-485 half-duplex communication screw terminal. MAX232 is used to convert the 5V power source to the needed voltage levels for RS-232. Any of the two serial ports on the microcontroller ATmega128 can be forwarded to the RS-232 terminal. There is a terminal for the connection of an Ethernet cable. A 100/10Base-T transformer/filter links this port to the Ethernet controller LAN91C111. The maximum cable length supported by the interface between an Ethernet board and a hub is about 100 meters. The 64-pin expansion port can accommodate the connection of additional boards. These boards could be simple I/O circuits that the Ethernut board controls, or they

may have their own microcontroller with the Ethernut board only serving as the Ethernet communicator.

Clocks and Watchdog

The ATmega128 system clock is generated by a 14.7456 MHz crystal. Instead, a 16-MHz crystal may also be used. A second 32.768 kHz crystal (Q2) maintains an on-chip asynchronous timer, which is generally employed as a software real-time clock. A separate 20-MHz crystal drives the Ethernet controller. The system may malfunction because of bugs in the software, short-term problems caused by electrical spikes or interference, or other problems. The watchdog timer built into the ATmega128 microcontroller resets the system if the program does not update it regularly.

Memories

The Ethernut board has different memory devices: flash ROM, static RAM, and EEPROM. The microcontroller ATmega128 has 128 kB of on-chip, non-volatile flash memory for storing the program and read-only data. This memory is 64K by 16 bits and is programmable using in-system instructions. There is a 512 kB static RAM (SRAM) on the Ethernut board, which can be utilized for read/write data storage. The lower 4 kB are used by the internal register and SRAM space of the ATmega128. The required address management is provided by a Xilinx CPLD XC9535XL programmed by egnite GmbH. The ATmega128's 16-bit address bus can only support upto to 64 kB of RAM. The microcontroller has 4 kB on-chip electrically erasable programmable read-only memory (EEPROM), which is commonly used for configuration data. The EEPROM memory is accessible for read/write operations under program control as well as via in-system programming. However, the time for writing EEPROM is significantly slower than that in Static RAM.

2. DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

2.2.2 Software Facilities of Nut/OS

The reliability of real-time computations in an operating system on an embedded system does not depend only on the logical integrity of the calculations, but also because the output is produced in real time. Such a requirement is achieved with a real-time operating system (RTOS) designed for real-time computations that can respond to events with predictable time constraints (see e.g. [18, 19]). When the time constraints are not satisfied, the real-time system is said to have failed. A real-time system has a set of tasks that it must execute, and one or some of those tasks may have a deadline that needs to be met, otherwise the system fails to work properly. In this project, we employ the Ethernut board as a DAQ system, which has a real-time operating system called Nut/OS with some capabilities: multithreading, event queues, dynamic memory allocation, timer management, stream I/O procedures, file system, and expandable device drivers (discussed in Chapter 4).

Ethernut's software is based on an open-source implementation of Nut/OS, a RTOS, and Nut/Net, a TCP/IP protocol suite. It makes the Ethernut board an ideal choice for the development of embedded Ethernet systems. Nut/Net is a TCP/IP stack which offers different protocols over Ethernet (ARP, IP, UDP, ICMP, PPP, and TCP), automatic configuration via dynamic host configuration protocol (DHCP), application programming interface (API) functions for various file access (HTTP, FTP, TFTP, SFTP, DNS, and Syslog), and API functions for different internet protocols (TCP and UDP socket). Because of these features, Nut/OS is a suitable RTOS for our Ethernut-based DAQ system, which is aimed at transmitting the neuromuscular blockade data collected from the ADC unit to a computer via an Ethernet cable for further anesthesia monitoring and control.

3

Analog-to-Digital Converter System

The functionality required by the measurement system being developed for monitoring neuromuscular blockade signals, namely EMG, MMG, and AMG, can be divided into three main operations: (1) data collection from EMG, MMG, and AMG sensors by the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) system; (2) data processing and packing by the Ethernet-based DAQ system; and (3) data transmission to a computer via an Ethernet network. We introduce the Ethernet-based DAQ system in the previous chapter. In this chapter, we describe how we designed and built a new ADC system with an SPI port that connects to the 64-pin expansion port of the Ethernet board. The data transmission via Ethernet and communication with a computer are discussed in the next chapter.

We developed an ADC unit with 8 analog channels using two 12-bit ADC devices to collect data from sensors. Each of the two 12-bit ADC devices, MAX1270 [20], has 8 channels and an SPI port for sending data to the microcontroller ATmega128 on the Ethernet-based DAQ system. The SPI protocol was chosen to ensure compatibility with as many ADC devices as possible. Moreover, the use of an SPI interface reduces the data load on the microcontroller associated with processing data from the ADC devices. The ATmega128 also has eight 10-bit ADC channels that are capable of rapid sampling rates in the kHz range [17]; however, 10-bit ADC and low sampling rates do not offer

3. ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER SYSTEM

us the high capabilities needed for this project. We used the device MAX1270, which is a 12-bit ADC with quick sampling rates up to 110 ksp/s. As we need to measure analog signals with two different voltage ranges (0 to +5 V, and -5 to +5 V), two MAX1270 devices were utilized. This system therefore has two integrated circuits (ICs; MAX1270) with the SPI interface, and the SPI port makes it possible to attach multiple ADC devices. The schematic circuit diagram of our final ADC board is presented in Appendix A, followed by its printed circuit board (PCB) in Appendix B; designed with the help of an electronic computer-aided design (ECAD) program, “Easily Applicable Graphical Layout Editor” (EAGLE) version 4.16r1 (see, e.g. [21, 22]), distributed by CadSoft GmbH.¹

Prior to data being accessed from an ADC with an SPI link, some extra processing must be performed by the microcontroller ATmega128, on the Ethernet-based DAQ system. It is required for the data recipient to know the beginning and end of a packet, as no hardware synchronization exists to indicate the start or end of data transmission. After decoding the received package and extracting the data, the microcontroller also needs to further process the data, such as reversing the byte order or joining various bytes, to create the correct numeric data in its memory.

After the sensor data is converted into a usable format, the microcontroller ATmega128 can perform additional processing. This could be data analysis, such as simply deriving root-mean-squared or a more complicated fast Fourier transform (FFT). However, our main aim in this project is to reduce the large volume of data received from multiple sensors to a useful format for simple data transmission over Ethernet.

Once the required configuration is done on the ADC system, the data is transmitted to the Ethernet-based DAQ system containing the microcontroller ATmega128, whose principal function is to communicate with a PC using network protocol. The Ethernet board incorporates the sensor data into a single

¹<http://www.cadsoft.de/>

stream for transmission to a computer via an Ethernet channel for visualization and storage. This requires packet encapsulation using a custom format. Via a TCP/IP socket, the encapsulated data can be sent to the computer.

3.1 Overview of the ADC Circuit

For this project, we designed and built a circuit board, which includes several electronic components such as MAX1270, LT1079, ADuM1201/2401, and TEL 3-1223. In particular, it contains two ADC MAX1270 devices: one with 0 to +5 V analog inputs, and another with ± 5 V. The IC MAX1270 is a multirange, 8-channel, serial 12-bit ADC [20], providing ADC in different voltage ranges with just a single +5V power supply, while input signals can be at their analog ranges above and below the supplied power. We also used some digital isolator devices, AduM1201 [23] and ADuM2401 [24], to isolate the direction of the electric current. These digital isolators are built by Analog Devices using high-speed complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) and monolithic transformer technologies [23, 24]. Both the ATmega128-based embedded Ethernet board manufactured by egnite GmbH and the MAX1270 ADC board designed by ourselves are essential parts of the project. The schematic development of our ADC board and its corresponding PCB were implemented using the program EAGLE v4.16r1 (see Appendixes A and B for the final design).

3.1.1 MAX1270: 12-bit ADC Device

MAX1270 is a multirange, 12-bit ADC chipset that needs only a single +5V supply to operate (see Fig.3.1). It can also work with analog signals, whose voltage range spans above and below +5V [20]. It has eight analog channels, which are separately programmable for a number of voltage ranges: ± 10 V, ± 5 V, 0 to +10 V, 0 to +5 V (see Appendix C). MAX1271 is a similar device with similar

3. ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER SYSTEM

Figure 3.1: A typical operating circuit for the 12-bit data-acquisition integrated circuit MAX1270 [20].

features, which can be programmed for the voltage ranges of $\pm V_{REF}$, $\pm V_{REF}/2$, 0 to V_{REF} , 0 to $V_{REF}/2$ based on the reference voltage of V_{REF} . Switching to a smaller range can increase the accuracy of measurements. This device powered by a single +5V system can easily measure analog inputs with 4–20 mA, ± 12 V, and ± 15 V provided by different sensors. Moreover, it has a fault protection of ± 16.5 V, which does protect the faulted channel from others. Additional features of MAX1270 are a 5 MHz track/hold bandwidth, a programmable internal or external clock, a 110 kbps throughput rate, and internal (4.096 V) or external reference operation [20].

Without any extra electronic device, MAX1270 directly connects to the SPI port of a microcontroller. For low-current shutdown between conversions, a hardware shutdown input ($\overline{\text{SHDN}}$), and two programmable power-down modes, standby (STBYPD) or full power-down (FULLPD), are available [20]. The ref-

Figure 3.2: A diagram of buffers in the micropower dual Op Amp LT1079 [25].

reference buffer stays active in standby mode to remove any startup delay.

The analog input ranges of both the devices MAX1270 and MAX1271 are configurable via software. By programming the appropriate bits (RNG, BIP) in the control byte, each analog input can be separately assigned to one of four ranges. The MAX1270 features selectable ranges based on 5 and 10 V, whereas the MAX1271 features extendable ranges based on the reference voltage (V_{REF}) supplied to the ADC reference-buffer (REF) pin.

3.1.2 LT1079: Op-Amp Buffers

To maintain the reliability of our measurement system, we need to buffer high-impedance sources. MAX1270 is compatible with optional quad operational-amplifier (op-amp) buffers. We chose the LT1079 (see Fig.3.2), which is a quad micropower op-amp buffer. To achieve micropower performance, sometimes accuracy, noise, and speed are sacrificed. However, the device LT1079 was designed to reduce supply current without compromising any metrics such as accuracy and speed, so it is a suitable choice for buffering. The LT1079 can function with a single power supply [25]. The input range can be below zero (ground). The all-NPN output stage can sink current while flowing to within a few mV of ground, which eliminates the need for pull-down resistors.

3. ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER SYSTEM

Figure 3.3: Functional block diagrams of the digital isolators ADuM1201 (top) and ADuM2401 (bottom) [23, 24].

3.1.3 ADuM1201/2401: Digital Isolators

The ADuM1201/ADuM12401 digital isolators [23, 24] have two/four separate isolation channels (see Fig.3.3) that can be set to different data speeds and have different channel settings. The supply voltage on either side of the ADuM1201/2401 devices ranges from 2.7 V to 5.5 V, which makes them compatible with low-voltage systems while performing voltage translation over the isolation barrier. Furthermore, they offer minimal pulse width distortion and extremely precise channel-to-channel matching. The ADuM1201/2401 technology contains a proprietary refresh unit that guarantees DC accuracy in the absence of any logic transition and during power-up and power-down situations, unlike alternative conventional optocouplers.

The ADuM1201/2401 digital isolator needs no extra electronic elements for the connection to the ADC MAX1270. However, it was suggested by the factory to bypass the power lines at the supply pins, so we connected some

Figure 3.4: Diagrams of DC-to-DC converters with: (a) single outputs, and (b) dual outputs [26].

bypass capacitors to the pins V_{DD1} and V_{DD2} of the isolators ADuM1201/2401 on our ADC circuit board. In systems with high transients, it is also necessary to minimize coupling across the isolation barrier on the PCB, so we considered it during the design of our PCB with the ECAD program EAGLE.

3.1.4 TEL 3-1223: DC-to-DC Converter

To adequately maintain the power consumption of our ADC board, we need to have an appropriate isolated DC/DC converter (see Fig. 3.4) based on the electric current usage of all the electronic elements on our ADC circuit board. For this purpose, we chose the TEL 3-1223 isolated DC/DC converter of the TEL 3 series, providing the isolation upto 3 Watt, manufactured by Traco Power. The power circuit also includes the three voltage regulators, namely LM7805, 7812, and 7912, which maintain steady constant voltages of +5, +12, and -12V, respectively; in addition, some capacitors for filtering ripple and noise in DC

3. ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER SYSTEM

Figure 3.5: A view of transmissions and speeds among the sensors, the ADC system, the Ethernet board, and the computer.

currents (see the schematic circuit diagram of our ADC system in Appendix A).

3.2 Communication with Ethernet-based DAQ

The egnite GmbH Ethernet board [27] is at the heart of our DAQ system. In addition to complete kernel and network API functions, the Ethernet Nut/OS also has headers for configuring the system and some API functions, which are discussed in detail in Chapter 4. We connect our ADC board to the 64-pin expansion port of the Ethernet board. We use one of the on-chip network modules on the embedded Ethernet system to establish a local host for uploading data to a computer. The program can also be debugged using an RS-232 cable connected to the computer. The IC MAX1270 from our ADC board is connected to the SPI module of the microcontroller ATmega128 on the Ethernet board through the expansion port, and data is transmitted to a local host via the Ethernet host.

Figure 3.5 presents a schematic of the connections between sensors, ADC unit, Ethernet-based DAQ system, and computer, as well as the speed of the communications. This only shows representative connections. We should note that our ADC board has many connectors (see Appendix A), which can be used depending on the needs of the specific application.

3.2. COMMUNICATION WITH ETHERNUT-BASED DAQ

Figure 3.6: An operating circuit for the Atmel Microcontroller ATmega128 [16].

As described in Chapter 2, the ATmega128 is an 8-bit microcontroller that is based on the enhanced RISC architecture of the AVR family [17]. The AVR core includes a broad instruction set with 32 working registers. All 32 registers are directly coupled to the Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU), providing access to two independent registers with a single command that runs in a single clock cycle. The ATmega128 offers many features such as 128kB of in-system programmable flash, 4kB of EEPROM, 4kB of SRAM, 53 digital I/O lines (see Fig. 3.6), 32 working registers, a real-time counter (RTC), 4 flexible timers and counters, 2 universal asynchronous receiver transmitters (USARTs), a 2-wire serial port, an 8-channel, programmable 10-bit ADC, a programmable watchdog timer, an SPI port, and a JTAG port for programming and testing. Furthermore, the on-chip debug system and programming access, along with six software selectable saving modes, are also included in this microcontroller.

3. ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER SYSTEM

Using an Atmel's AVR family microcontroller and a Xilinx CPLD, egnite GmbH developed the embedded Ethernet system. The on-chip ISP port in ATmega128 enables in-system reprogramming of the flash memory via an SPI interface, a standard memory programmer, or an on-chip boot program being executed on the AVR core. The boot program on the microcontroller ATmega128 can use any available programming interface to download the program into the flash memory. Combining an 8-bit RISC CPU with self-programmable flash on a single chip, the Atmel ATmega128 is a unique microcontroller that is capable of adjustable and cost-effective embedded controller applications. The AVR family is also supported by a comprehensive set of programming tools, such as C compilers, assemblers, debuggers, and emulators.

To configure our ADC unit and retrieve data from it, we programmed the microcontroller ATmega128 on the Ethernet-based DAQ system. The ATmega128 can run 16 million instructions per second (MIPS) with 4 kB of RAM. More details about the ATmega128 are available in its data sheet (see [17]). We uploaded our program written in C into the microcontrollers using the JTAG port from our computer. We developed our program using the WinAVR [28] development environment distributed by GCC [29]. This C compiler is capable of producing optimized code and supports most of the ANSI C standard.

The Ethernet board has an LAN91C111 device [30], which supports the third generation of embedded fast Ethernet networking. The third generation offers reliability and flexibility in Ethernet connectivity solutions. The LAN91C111 is a mixed-signal analog/digital chipset with the MAC and PHY portions of the 10 and 100 Mbps protocols. This architecture helps facilitate extended data throughput in embedded applications hosted in 32-bit, 16-bit, or 8-bit format [27]. In the next chapter, we describe how a local host is set up on the Ethernet board with the help of Nut/OS API functions so that the ATmega128 microcontroller can provide a structured stream of the sensor data received from our ADC system.

4

Nut/OS and ADC Device Driver

As previously mentioned, three main tasks are required to be accomplished in our microcontroller-based system developed for anesthesia monitoring: ADC data collection, DAQ data handling, and data transmission to a computer. The first two tasks, which are primary hardware, are explained in Chapters 2 and 3. The last part, which is implemented as software in the application program of the AVR microcontroller ATmega128, is discussed in this chapter. This includes data transmission via Ethernet and communication with a computer. We used Nut/OS version 4.2.1 (revision 1.39.2.2), released on October 17, 2006, which is compatible with the Ethernut board version 2.1. In the next section, we provide an overview of some application programming interface (API) functions of the Nut/OS kernel and network libraries, followed by a section on the *device driver* program we developed for the MAX1270-based ADC system to properly work within the real-time operating system Nut/OS.

4.1 Nut/OS: Ethernut Real-time Operating System

In the subsections that follow, we give a brief overview of a few API functions of the kernel and network libraries of the real-time operating system Nut/OS operating on the Ethernut board (see [31] for more information). The ker-

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

nel library includes several useful API functions for managing threads, timers, events, interrupts, and the file system, as well as declaring a new device driver. The network library contains some API functions for initializing the Ethernet network, establishing a server, and allocating network buffers.

4.1.1 Kernel API Functions

Before the program can be started, the real-time operating system needs to complete a series of initialization steps, which are included in the `nutinit` module. It starts an idle thread, which then initializes the timer functions. Memory and thread management are also initialized during this process. At this point, the main thread of the program looks like:

```
#include <compiler.h>
int main(void)
{
    for (;;)
}
```

where `compiler.h` is the header file required for working with the AVR-GCC compiler, which configures the stack pointer on the entrance to the main routine `main()`. Using this header, the main routine is changed to `NutAppMain`. The compiler header file `compiler.h` contains most of the necessary Nut/OS header files, so no additional header files need to be included in the main program.

Thread Management

Most of the time, Nut/OS needs to work on more than one task at the same time. To fulfill this requirement, Nut/OS offers light processes called *threads* [32]. Nut/OS is able to switch the use of the CPU from one thread to another. This provides the impression that threads are executed simultaneously. Each thread has its own priority, and that priority is what determines how important it is. This priority can range from 0 to 255, with 0 being the highest priority and 255 representing the lowest priority.

All of the threads are running in the same memory space and sharing the same resources, which is expected to drastically lower the cost of switching overhead. However, two or more threads sometime need to access the same resource simultaneously, like memory addresses or external devices, this could make a problem. It is essential to prevent them from making problems for each other by accessing the same resource at the same time. Cooperative multi-threading is a feature implemented in Nut/OS that ensures that threads are not confined to a fixed time-slice in any way. They are not suddenly stopped unless they are waiting for a special event or actively releasing the CPU usage, unless a CPU interrupt signal is received.

As previously mentioned, the main thread is already working as a thread alongside the invisible background idle thread. By invoking `NutThreadCreate`, a new thread is created. The code operating as a thread is simply a C-code routine. To conceal platform-specific details, applications should declare these routines using the `THREAD` macro as follows:

```

THREAD(Thread1, arg)
{
    for (;;)
    {
        NutSleep(125);
    }
}
int main(void)
{
    NutThreadCreate("t1", Thread1, 0, 512);
    for (;;)
    {
        NutSleep(125);
    }
}

```

In this example, the API function `NutSleep` introduces a halt in the loop for 125 milliseconds. If one of the loops does not invoke this or another similar blocking function, such as reading from a device or waiting for an event, the other threads cannot obtain access to the CPU.

In Nut/OS, the thread starting point is declared as a function, which has no

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

return:

```
void threadfn(void *arg) __attribute__((noreturn));
```

The void pointer argument is utilized to transfer a specific data to the thread.

The header file `thread.h` contains a macro that simplifies function declaration:

```
THREAD(threadfn, arg)
```

A specific API function called `NutMain()` should be present in each Nut/OS application program:

```
THREAD(NutMain, arg)
```

whose function is similar to the standard C function `main()`.

During the initialization process, the function `NutMain()` is automatically called. This function serves as the beginning of the main thread. The primary thread can then initiate the creation of other threads by invoking the function `NutThreadCreate()` with the following declaration and arguments:

```
NutThreadCreate(u_char *name, void (*fn)(void *),  
               void *arg, u_short stackSize);
```

The first argument `name` declares the string name of a new thread. The next one `fn` is a pointer being linked to the function that serves as the entry point for the new thread. The last argument, `arg`, is a void pointer declaring the stack size allocated to this function and can be null if it is not being used.

The priority of a thread can be set with a number between 0 and 255, with the lowest number being the most important [32]. When a thread is created, it has a priority of 64. In contrast to other operating systems, Nut/OS threads can alter their own priorities, but not those of other threads. The API function declaration for this purpose is:

```
u_char NutThreadSetPriority(u_char level);
```

Moreover, Nut/Net networking functions each have their own threads, which execute with the pre-selected priorities listed in Table 4.1.

Context switching within Nut/OS is performed by two functions as follows:

```
void NutThreadEntry(void) __attribute__((naked));  
NutThreadSwitch(void);
```

Table 4.1: Priorities of Nut/Net Networking Threads [32].

Threads	String Name	Priority	Stack Size
Ethernet Transmitter	txi5	7	640
Ethernet Receiver	rxix	8	640
ARP Table Expiration	arpex	64	384
TCP State Timer	tcptmr	64	384
DHCP Client	dhcp	254	512
Idle Thread	idle	255	384

These two API functions are primarily composed of inline assembly codes. The function `NutThreadSwitch()` pushes 32 registers into the stack and then stores the stack pointer in the `NUTTHREADINFO` structure of the thread that is being halted. Afterwards, it loads the stack pointer from the `NUTTHREADINFO` structure of the thread and pops 32 registers out of the stack [32].

We should note that once a thread is created, it pushes data into the stack. The stack is initialized by the API function `NutThreadCreate()` in such a way that looks like the thread has already been switched. It also allocates one heap of memory for each thread. This block's size is the size of the stack plus the size of the `NUTTHREADINFO` structure.

Timer Management

Nut/OS includes API functions for the time service such as `NutTimerInit()` and `NutSleep(u_long ms)`. The former initializes the system timer, and the latter halts that thread for the number specified in milliseconds. Invoking `NutSleep()` allows us to delay the thread for a given time. In particular, the function `NutSleep()` calls another function called `NutTimerStart()` declared as follows:

```
HANDLE NutTimerStart(u_long ms, void (*callback)(HANDLE, void *),
                    void *arg, u_char flags);
```

which creates a new timer. To terminate a timer, we simply use:

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

```
void NutTimerStop(HANDLE handle);
```

To have delays in some millisecond, we can use the following delay routine:

```
void NutDelay(u_char ms);
```

which functions based on the CPU speed. In other cases, where we need the CPU speed, `NutGetCpuClock` provides access to the CPU clock in Hertz.

Event Management

Threads have the ability to post or broadcast events to other threads, as well as wait for events from other threads or interrupts. Nut/OS offers an event queue manager. While a thread is waiting for an event, it can queue up in one of these queues, and other threads can post events to these queues in order to wake up the threads that are waiting. To have a better understanding of the event management in Nut/OS, we can look at the following simple example:

```
HANDLE evt_h;
THREAD(Thread1, arg)
{
    for (;;)
    {
        NutSleep(125);
        NutPostEvent(&evt_h);
    }
}
int main(void)
{
    NutThreadCreate("t1", Thread1, 0, 192);
    for (;;)
    {
        NutEventWait(&evt_h, NUT_WAIT_INFINITE);
    }
}
```

In this example, `Thread1` is executing an infinite cycle of sleeps. The main thread expects an event posted to a queue. Event queues are declared by a variable `evt_h` defined using `HANDLE`. The main thread's cycle is blocked by `NutEventWait()` and awoken whenever `Thread1` posts an event.

Involving `NutEventPost(HANDLE *qhp)`, events can be posted to a queue. If there are already one or more threads waiting on this queue, the first is

removed from the queue, and it is then ready to execute. Because this thread was placed at the top of the priority-ordered queue, it has automatically been given the highest priority. In the event that there are no items in the queue, it transitions into a special state known as signaled. If a thread needs to wait on a signaled queue, it keeps in ready-to-run mode even if the queue has been signaled. Invoking `NutEventBroadcast (HANDLE *qhp)` awakes all threads on the given queue.

The API function `NutEventWait ()` has the following declaration:

```
int NutEventWait (HANDLE *qhp, u_long ms);
```

This function halts the calling thread and adds it to the queue specified by the first argument `qhp`. The second parameter `ms` is used to specify the waiting time in milliseconds. If the specified waiting time passes without an event being added to the queue, the thread is available to execute immediately.

Interrupts

Interrupt functions are executed promptly when interrupts are enabled, even if the active thread is unwilling to transfer the CPU control to another thread. The API functions listed below can be called by interrupt functions:

```
void NutEventPostAsync (HANDLE *qhp);  
void NutEventBroadcastAsync (HANDLE *qhp);
```

They operate identically to their synchronous counterparts, but with any final context switch. They alter the wait queue and prepare threads for execution. The interrupted thread resumes execution once the CPU has completed executing the interrupt function. It is conceivable for a thread with a lower priority to be running while a thread with a higher priority is set to run. Directly or indirectly, as soon as the active thread invokes the API function `NutThreadYield()`, the CPU is allocated to the thread with the high priority.

It should be enough to clear the interrupt enable flag in the status register to turn off the interrupt. But turning interrupts back on when it is done could

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

confuse the calling function if it needs to work with interrupts off. The following two API functions can maintain the interrupt status between nested functions:

```
void NutEnterCritical(void);  
void NutExitCritical(void);
```

The former function turns off interrupts and puts the status register's contents on the stack, whereas the latter function restores the status register's contents.

File System

Webservers are already built with a file system, so Nut/OS does not need one. Nut/OS provides a very simplistic file system called UROM, where files are located in the code ROM, to facilitate programming. The Create UROM utility (`crurrom`) is employed to turn directories into C source files, which are then compiled and integrated with our application program.

Device Drivers

Device drivers can have their own interrupt, delay, or callback functions by calling the API function `NutRegisterIrqHandler`. They can be written as Nut/OS extensions or as applications. In contrast to desktop operating systems, real-time operating systems in embedded devices do not have a memory management unit that can protect memory addresses and access to I/O ports. Because of this, Nut/OS does not have a specific “kernel mode” similar to desktop operating systems in which device drivers can run. Thus, there is no specific kernel-mode requirement for a device driver in embedded systems, and any application can easily have access to all available resources. Embedded Ethernet devices for controller applications may include numerous inputs and outputs. Using stream I/O devices allows for a code that is nearly device-independent, so Nut/OS drivers only exist for the extended purposes of additional devices attached to the 64-pin expansion post.

Nut/OS has its own library, `nutcrt`, which replaces the compiler's runtime

library's functions. This set of functions simplifies the porting of many existing desktop applications. Nevertheless, there is a significant distinction between standard C applications written for desktop computers and those for embedded systems. Embedded systems typically do not pre-define services for `stdin`, `stdout` and `stderr`. For example, the simplest 'Hello world' program needs some additional lines to work on Nut/OS:

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <dev/usartavr.h>
int main(void)
{
    unsigned long baud = 115200;
    // Register the device
    NutRegisterDevice(&devUsartAvr0, 0, 0);
    // Assign the device to stdout.
    freopen("uart0", "w", stdout);
    // Set the baud rate of the serial port (Optional).
    _ioctl(_fileno(stdout), UART_SETSPEED, &baud);
    printf("Hello world!\n");
}
```

Combining Nut/OS and compiler libraries for standard C functions is sometimes problematic. We need to check the linker map file to ensure if our application pauses in the `stdio` functions or crashes during invoke. If they do not work, `nutcert` could have been omitted from the libraries supplied for the compiler.

4.1.2 Network API Functions

Prior to using the Nut/OS network library called *Nut/Net* in our application program, the network device driver must first be registered by invoking the network API procedure `NutRegisterDevice` and the network interface must be configured by calling the function `NutDhcpIfConfig` or another similar API function [33]. With the API function `NutDhcpIfConfig`, the program can obtain the local IP address, network mask, and default gateway from a DHCP server. This function uses the configuration stored in the on-chip EEPROM of the AVR microcontroller if the DHCP server does not respond within a certain amount of milliseconds. The API procedure `NutDhcpIfConfig` utilizes the IP address

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

present in the header of an ICMP packet if the EEPROM does not have any valid addresses. In this case, the `netmask` is set to `255.255.255.0`, and there is no default gateway setup.

Network Initialization

By making a call to `NutNetIfConfig`, our programs can set up a static IP address and network mask. Alternatively, applications can use `NutDhcpIfConfig` and `NutNetIfConfig` in conjunction with one another. There are two IP addresses that are saved in EEPROM: a soft one and a hard one. The most recently used IP address becomes the soft IP address. In the case that Ethernut is rebooted when there is no DHCP server accessible, the soft IP address is again used. The function `NutDhcpIfConfig` does not send out any DHCP queries if a hard IP address is stored in EEPROM. Instead, it uses the hard IP address immediately. The following simple code shows how these configurations are done:

```
if (NutDhcpIfConfig("eth0", 0, 60000))
{
    u_char my_mac[] = { 0x00, 0x06, 0x98, 0x20, 0x00, 0x00 };
    if (NutDhcpIfConfig("eth0", my_mac, 60000))
    {
        u_long ip_addr = inet_addr("192.168.192.100");
        u_long ip_mask = inet_addr("255.255.255.0");
        NutNetIfConfig("eth0", my_mac, ip_addr, ip_mask);
    }
}
```

The first call of `NutDhcpIfConfig` does not have a MAC address as an argument. If it is found in the EEPROM, the function queries the DHCP server for the associated IP settings and returns 0. Otherwise, it returns `-1`; however, we do not know if this is because DHCP was unsuccessful or because the EEPROM does not have a valid MAC address. Hence, the function `NutDhcpIfConfig` is again used, but with a hard-coded MAC address. If it fails once more, then we ensure that the content of the EEPROM is invalid and no DHCP server is available. To setup the network interface, the last command manually configures the MAC address, IP address, and IP mask using the API procedure `NutNetIfConfig`.

4.1. NUT/OS: ETHERNUT REAL-TIME OPERATING SYSTEM

Two procedures, `NutRegisterDevice` and `NutNetIfConfig`, are used to set up the Ethernet hardware before it can be used. The first thing that has to be done is register the device. All of the required hardware procedures and data structures are added once we make a call to the `NutRegisterDevice` procedure. The I/O port address and interrupt number arguments are due to historical reasons and are ignored by most devices:

```
NutRegisterDevice(&devEth0, 0, 0);
```

The device information for the LAN device driver is store in `devEth0`. It has data like the name of the device (`eth0`), the type of this interface (`IFTYPNET`), and so on. It also has the location of the hardware initialization procedure. Some data structures are set up, and the hardware controller is initialized with `NutRegisterDevice`. Some configurations are necessary for network devices, which is done by invoking the API function `NutNetIfConfig`:

```
NutNetIfConfig("eth0", mac, 0, 0);
```

The first argument is the registered device's name. The second one provides a 6-byte array containing the Ethernet controller's MAC address. A MAC address, also known as a hardware address or an Ethernet address, is a unique number assigned to each Ethernet node. IEEE Standards Office assigns the topmost 24 bits as the manufacturer ID. The board ID for egnite GmbH's Ethernut boards is `000698hex`. The lower 24 bits represent the unique ID assigned to the board by its manufacturer. The address is saved in EEPROM by Nut/Net, but we can also define it using a static variable in the application:

```
static u_char mac[] = { 0x00,0x06,0x98,0x09,0x09,0x09 };
```

The two remaining parameters of `NutNetIfConfig` are used to specify the minimum IP (Internet Protocol) information, the IP address of our node, and the network mask. In our example, we simply set both to zero, which invokes a DHCP client to query this information from a DHCP server in the local network. Therefore it may take some seconds until the call returns, depending on the response time of the DHCP server. The `NutNetIfConfig` function needs two more

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

arguments: the IP address of our node and the network mask. These parameters are used to give the Internet Protocol (IP) the least amount of information it needs. In the example above, we just set both of them to zero, which turns on a DHCP client and makes it to ask a DHCP server on the local network for this information. Because of this, the time it takes for the call to be returned might vary widely depending on how quickly the DHCP server responds. For example, to assign the IP address `192.168.171.2` with the network mask `255.255.255.0`, dial, we just call:

```
NutNetIfConfig("eth0", mac, inet_addr("192.168.171.2"),
               inet_addr("255.255.255.0"));
```

The procedure `NutNetIfConfig` initializes the Ethernet controller device and then turns on the LAN LED light on the Ethernut board if it is connected correctly. At this stage, Ethernut responds to ping requests:

```
#include <dev/nicrtl.h>
#include <sys/timer.h>
#include <arpa/inet.h>
static u_char mac[] = { 0x00,0x06,0x98,0x09,0x09,0x09 };
int main(void)
{
    NutRegisterDevice(&devEth0, 0x8300, 5);
    NutNetIfConfig("eth0", mac, 0, 0);
    for(;;)
    {
        NutSleep(500);
    }
}
```

Network Communication

TCP/IP programs can have two roles: server or client. Servers wait for incoming connection requests on a particular port number, which is referred to as the port number. Nut/Net automatically chooses the port numbers for clients. For both the TCP and UDP protocols, Nut/Net offers a socket API [33]. Calling either `NutTcpCreateSocket` or `NutUdpCreateSocket` is the first thing that has to be done in order to successfully establish a socket. Then, TCP server programs

call the `NutTcpAccept` function with the given port number. This call waits until a TCP client program attempts to connect to that port number before blocking until the connection is made. When a connection has been made between the two parties, they communicate with one another by using `NutTcpSend` and `NutTcpReceive`. For example, a simple network communication in a TCP client may be done using the following lines:

```
TCP_SOCKET *sock = NutTcpCreateSocket();
NutTcpConnect(sock, inet_addr("192.168.192.2"), 80);
NutTcpSend(sock, "Hello\r\n", 7);
NutTcpReceive(sock, buff, sizeof(buff));
NutTcpCloseSocket(sock);
```

Similarly, a simple network communication in a TCP server may be established:

```
TCP_SOCKET *sock = NutTcpCreateSocket();
NutTcpAccept(sock, 80);
NutTcpReceive(sock, buff, sizeof(buff));
NutTcpSend(sock, "2U2\r\n", 5);
NutTcpCloseSocket(sock);
```

Attaching TCP connections to conventional I/O streams is also possible with the Nut/OS operating system. To attach a connected socket to a Nut/OS stream:

```
stream = _fdopen((int)((uptr_t) sock), "r+b");
```

Applications can also use `fprintf`, `fputs`, `fscanf`, and `fgets`, as well as other `stdio` functions, to communicate via a TCP socket.

We need a TCP socket to communicate through TCP. This socket, which is created by calling the API function `NutTcpCreateSocket()`, has a data structure that stores all information on the state of a connection between two applications. This function returns a pointer to the data structure after allocating it from heap memory and initializing it. Then, we need to specify if the role of the client or the server is assumed in the ongoing communication. As a client, we try to establish a connection with the host supplied on the specified port number. The following example shows how to connect to the host with the IP address of `192.168.171.1` using port `12345`:

```
NutTcpConnect(sock, inet_addr("192.168.171.1"), 12345);
```

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

If we intend to accept the server, we simply use the following line:

```
NutTcpAccept(sock, 12345);
```

This call remains blocked until a client makes a connection. As soon as that occurs, we are able to transmit data to the client by making a call to `NutTcpSend` and receive data from the client by using `NutTcpReceive`.

Nut/OS provides the standard I/O library functions to support stream devices. To take advantage of them, we need to connect a TCP socket to a stream:

```
FILE *stream; stream = _fdopen((int)sock, "r+b");
```

This device may be used in the same way that any other Nut/OS stream device can be utilized, and it makes the input and output. When a client has successfully connected to a server, the server may send out a welcome message:

```
fprintf(stream, "200 Welcome to Ethernut\r\n");
```

The client has the option of disconnecting themselves or, more commonly, sending a special instruction to the server that causes it to disconnect. The following line used by the server to terminate the stream

```
fclose(stream);  
NutTcpCloseSocket(sock);
```

The first line releases all memory allocated to the stream, and the second line is used to close the socket terminal.

Our program can also make use of a network buffer structure. It is made up of four substructures that have all the similar format. Each of them stores a reference to a data buffer as well as the size of the buffer itself. Each of them corresponds to a distinct protocol layer, datalink layer, network layer, transport layer, and application layer, respectively. An extra flag field added to the structure of the network buffer is used to determine whether or not the related buffer has been dynamically allocated. Using the API functions `NutNetBufAlloc` and `NutNetBufFree`, network buffers can be allocated and deleted, respectively. Each time a new packet arrives at the network interface, the driver creates a network buffer. This buffer contains all of the data that is stored in the datalink

substructure. After that, the Ethernet layer will split this buffer before forwarding the packet on to an Internet Protocol (IP) address or an Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) layer by just setting the pointer of the network buffer substructure beyond the Ethernet header and modifying the buffer lengths.

4.2 MAX1270 ADC Device Driver

To have our MAX1270-based ADC system work with the Ethernet board, we developed a device driver program for it on the operating system Nut/OS. As described in Chapter 3, we built a new ADC board using two MAX1270 ICs. The PCB of our ADC system is designed with the aid of the ECAD program EAGLE. Our ADC circuit board also includes op-amp buffers (LT1079), digital isolators (ADuM1201/2401), DC-to-DC converter (TEL3-1223), and voltage regulators (LM7805, 7812, and 7912). However, we only need to establish communication with two MAX1270 ICs via their SPI ports connected to the 64-pin expansion port of the Ethernet board. The MAX1270 device driver program developed in this project has two files named `max1270.c` and `max1270.h`, which contain API functions for initialization and communication with the two 8-Channel 12-Bit ADC MAX1270 ICs via the SPI port of the microcontroller.

We use the procedure `Port_Init()` to initialize the input/output directions and primary value (zero/high impedance) in the port pins as follows:

```
void Port_Init(void)
{
    PORTB = ADC_Disel;
    DDRB = 0x37;
}
```

We then have three sets of API functions in our ADC device driver, namely SPI communication, ADC functions, and delay functions.

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

Figure 4.1: Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) Bus [14].

4.2.1 SPI API Functions

We employ the procedure `SPI_Init()` to initialize and set the control registers of the SPI port (see Fig. 4.1) as follows:

```
void SPI_Init(void)
{
    SPCR = (1<<SPE) | (1<<MSTR) | (1<<SPR0);
    SPSR = 0x00; //setup SPI
}
```

We consider the bits of the SPI Control Register (SPCR), which are configured as follows [17]:

- **Bit 7** – The SPI Interrupt Enable (SPIE) bit leads to the SPI interrupt when the SPIF bit in the SPI Status Register (SPSR) is active and the if the global interrupt enable bit in SREG is active.
- **Bit 6** – The SPI Enable (SPE) bit activates the SPI operations.
- **Bit 5** – The Data Order (DORD) bit if activated indicates that the Least significant bit (LSB) of the data should be transmitted first. When the DORD bit is written to zero, the most significant bit (MSB) of the data is transmitted first.
- **Bit 4** – The Master/Slave Select (MSTR) bit chooses between SPI master mode (1) and slave mode (0). If the \overline{SS} port on the SPI bus is used as an input, it is driven low when the MSTR is activated, MSTR is cleared, and

the SPIF bit in the SPSR is activated. It is necessary to enable MSTR in order to re-activate master mode.

- **Bit 3** – The Clock Polarity (CPOL) bit is enabled (1) when we require the SCLK on the SPI bus is high for idle. When the CPOL bit is disabled (0), the SCLK is low for idle:

CPOL	Leading edge	Trailing edge
0	Rising	Falling
1	Falling	Rising

- **Bit 2** – The Clock Phase (CPHA) decides if data is sampled on the leading (first) or trailing (last) edge of the SCLK:

CPHA	Leading edge	Trailing edge
0	Sample	Setup
1	Setup	Sample

- **Bits 1, 0** – The SPI Clock Rate Select 1 and 0 (SPR1 and SPR0) configures the SCLK of the device in master mode, but they have no effect on the slave. The correspondence between SCLK and the oscillator clock frequency (f_{osc}) based on SPI2X, SPR1, SPR0 is as follows:

SPI2X	SPR1	SPR0	SCLK Frequency
0	0	0	$f_{osc}/4$
0	0	1	$f_{osc}/16$
0	1	0	$f_{osc}/64$
0	1	1	$f_{osc}/128$
1	0	0	$f_{osc}/2$
1	0	1	$f_{osc}/8$
1	1	0	$f_{osc}/32$
1	1	1	$f_{osc}/64$

We also should note that the bits of the SPI Status Register (SPSR) are set as follows (see [17] for detailed descriptions):

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

- **Bit 7** – The SPI Interrupt Flag (SPIF) is set when a serial transfer is fulfilled. An interrupt is created if the SPIE bit in the SPCR and global interrupts are enabled. If \overline{SS} is used as an input and is driven low when the SPI is in master mode, which also sets the SPIF flag. The SPIF is cleared by hardware when the interrupt handling vector is executed. The SPIF bit can also be cleared by first reading the SPSR with the SPIF set and afterward accessing the SPI Data Register (SPDR).
- **Bit 6** – The Write COLLision flag (WCOL) is activated when the SPDR is written during a data transfer. The WCOL flag (and the SPIF) are cleared by first reading the SPSR with the WCOL set after accessing the SPDR.
- **Bits 5...1** – These bits are reserved and always return zero.
- **Bit 0** – The Double SPI Speed (SPI2X) bit is enable (1) to double the SPI speed (SCLK Frequency) when the SPI is in master mode, meaning that the minimum SCLK period is twice CPU clock periods. If the SPI is set to slave mode, the SPI is only operated upto $f_{osc}/4$.

We also note that the SPI port of the ATmega128 may also be utilized for uploading or downloading the EEPROM memory. The SPI Data Register (SPDR; see [17] for details) is a read/write buffer for data transfer between the register file and the SPI Shift Register. While writing to the SPDR initiates data transmission, reading it causes the Shift Register Receive to be read.

We utilize the function `SpiWriteDataReg()` to write a byte into the SPDR:

```
void SpiWriteDataReg(unsigned char byte)
{
    SPDR = byte;
}
```

and the function `SpiReadDataReg()` to read a byte from the SPDR:

```
unsigned char SpiReadDataReg(void)
{
    return SPDR;
}
```

We use the function `SPITransmit()` to transmit a byte into the SPDR and

waits for the transmission:

```
void SPITransmit( unsigned char data )
{
    if ( SPITransmitting ) // prevent false SPIF clears from
        waitForTransmission(); // hanging the wait loop
    SPDR = data; // start transmission of data
    SPITransmitting = 1; // flag transmission is in progress
}
```

and the function `SPIReceive()` to retrieve byte from the SPDR and hold until the transmission done:

```
unsigned char SPIReceive( unsigned char data )
{
    if (SPITransmitting)
        waitForTransmission();
    // #define in SPI.h
    delay_us( 3 );
    // give the ATmega128 time to prepare return data
    SPDR = data; // start bidirectional transfer
    waitForTransmission(); // #define in SPI.h
    // reading SPCR and SPDR will clear SPIF, so we use this flag
    // to indicate that we are currently transmitting
    SPITransmitting = 0;
    return SPDR;
}
```

In the routine `SPIReceive()`, we need to have a delay of $3\ \mu\text{s}$ for preparation. To have delays, we include two delay functions in microsecond and millisecond as described in § 4.2.3.

4.2.2 ADC API Functions

The device MAX1270 has a programmable register that is used to configure the channel, range, polarity, power-down, and clock (see Appendix C). We use the procedure `Init_ADC()` to initialize the MAX1270 device for a given channel (channel: between 0 and 7) with the specified voltage range and polarity (rang_polar), as well as supply and clock modes (pw_clk):

```
void Init_ADC(unsigned char start, unsigned char channel, unsigned
    char rang_polar, unsigned char pw_clk)
{
    unsigned char tmp;
    tmp=start | channel | rang_polar | pw_clk;
```

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

```
SPITransmit(tmp);  
}
```

For the voltage range and polarity (`rang_polar`), the following configuration values are chosen:

```
#define ADC_HALFR_UNIP 0x00<<2  
#define ADC_HALFR_BIP 0x01<<2  
#define ADC_FULLLR_UNIP 0x02<<2  
#define ADC_FULLLR_BIP 0x03<<2
```

which can configure the range and polarity of MAX1270 as follows:

Value	Range
ADC_HALFR_UNIP	0 to +5V
ADC_FULLLR_UNIP	0 to +10V
ADC_HALFR_BI	±5V
ADC_FULLLR_BIP	±10V

For the supply and clock modes (`pw_clk`), the following configuration values are considered:

```
#define ADC_NORMP_INTCLK 0x00  
#define ADC_NORMP_EXTCLK 0x01  
#define ADC_STBYPD 0x02  
#define ADC_FULLLPD 0x03
```

which provide the following power-down and clock selection in MAX1270:

Value	Mode
ADC_NORMP_INTCLK	Normal operation, internal clock mode
ADC_NORMP_EXTCLK	Normal operation, external clock mode
ADC_STBYPD	Standby power-down, unaffected clock mode
ADC_FULLLPD	Full power-down

We made the following function `Read_ADC()` for retrieving the results from ADC1 or ADC2 specified by the ADC device number (`num`: 0 or 1) through the SPI bus for the given channel number of MAX1270 (`channel`: between 0 and 7) and the defined voltage range and polarity (`rang_polar`):

```
unsigned int Read_ADC(unsigned char num,
```

```

        unsigned char channel,
        unsigned char rang_polar)
{
    unsigned int result=0;
    switch (num)
    {
        case 0:
            PORTB = ADC_Sel_CS1;
            break;
        case 1:
            PORTB = ADC_Sel_CS2;
            break;
        default:;
    }
    Init_ADC(ADC_START, channel<<4, rang_polar, ADC_NORMP_EXTCLK);
    result=SPIReceive(0);
    result=(result<<9) + (SPIReceive(0)<<1);
    result+= (SPIReceive(0)>>7) & 0x01;
    SPIReceive(0);
    PORTB = ADC_Disel;
    return result;
}

```

4.2.3 Delay API Functions

As mentioned in § 4.2.1, we require 3 μ s delay for preparation in `SPIReceive()`. To have delays in microsecond and millisecond, we include two functions, which are mainly composed of inline assembly codes. The task `delay_us()` suspends the current thread for the given value in microsecond:

```

void delay_us(unsigned int microseconds)
{
    if (microseconds == 0)
        return;
    __asm__ volatile (
        "1: push r22" "\n\t"
        " ldi r22, 4" "\n\t"
        "2: dec r22" "\n\t"
        " brne 2b" "\n\t"
        " pop r22" "\n\t"
        " sbiw %0, 1" "\n\t"
        " brne 1b"
        : "=w" ( microseconds )
        : "0" ( microseconds )
    );
}

```

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

If a value of zero is used, the current thread hands over the remainder of its allocated time to another thread with equal priority that is expected to run. If no threads of equal priority are available, the task is instantly completed and the current thread continues its function.

Similarly, The task `delay_ms()` halts the current thread for the given value in millisecond:

```
void delay_ms(unsigned int time_ms)
{
    if (time_ms == 0)
        return;
    __asm__ volatile (
        "1: push r22" "\n\t"
        " ldi r22, 84" "\n\t"
        "2: push r23" "\n\t"
        " ldi r23, 77" "\n\t"
        "3: dec r23" "\n\t"
        " brne 3b" "\n\t"
        " pop r23" "\n\t"
        " dec r22" "\n\t"
        " brne 2b" "\n\t"
        " pop r22" "\n\t"
        " sbiw %0, 1" "\n\t"
        " brne 1b"
        : "=w" (time_ms)
        : "0" (time_ms)
    );
}
```

It has the same functionality as `delay_us()` when a value of zero is applied.

4.3 Tailored HTTP Server Application

We modified the sample HTTP server program (`httpd`) by egnite Software GmbH included in the Ethernet applications of Nut/OS v4.2.1. Its folder contains a C file named `httpserv.c` (rev. 1.15; September 7, 2006) and a compiler `Makefile`. We made a copy from `httpd`, added the ADC device driver files (`max1270.c` and `max1270.h`) to the new copy, and tailored the main thread and HTTP service thread in the C program `httpserv.c` based on the requirements of our project. We used the programming tool by the Atmel AVR Studio for writing our modi-

fied codes into the microcontroller ATmega128 on the Ethernut system.

4.3.1 Initialization in Main Thread

In the main thread, we need to initialize the port and SPI controller:

```
Port_Init();  
SPI_Init();
```

Then, we register the Ethernet controller device driver:

```
NutRegisterDevice(&DEV_ETHER, 0, 0);
```

We set the network configuration for the Ethernut Board:

```
NutNetIfConfig(DEV_ETHER_NAME, mac, ip_addr, ip_mask) == 0)
```

Then, we need to register our device for the file system:

```
NutRegisterDevice(&MY_FSDEV, 0, 0);
```

The threads for the HTTP (port 80) and TCP (port 100) are created as follows:

```
NutThreadCreate("httpd0", HTTPService,  
                (void *) (uptr_t) i, NUT_THREAD_MAINSTACK);  
NutThreadCreate("tcpadc", TCPService, NULL, NUT_THREAD_MAINSTACK);
```

The priority of the main thread is set to low:

```
NutThreadSetPriority(254);
```

Finally, an interrupt of one minute (60 sec) is included in the main thread using

```
NutSleep(60000).
```

4.3.2 Configuration in HTTP Service Thread

The file `httpserv.c` contains routines for HTTP and TCP and communications.

The Ethernut board uses the following IP setting in communications:

```
#define MY_IPADDR "192.168.192.35" // Unique IP address  
#define MY_IPMASK "255.255.255.0" // IP network mask  
#define MY_IPGATE "192.168.192.1" //Gateway IP address
```

The following TCP/IP setting in the computer is used to get the connection:

- IP address: 192.168.0.10 or 192.168.0.35
- Subnet mask: 255.255.255.0

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

- Default gateway: 192.168.192.1

and in the web browser: `http://192.168.0.170/`

We create a special thread for HTTP server (port 80):

```
THREAD(HTTPService, arg);
```

by invoking the API function `NutThreadCreate()`:

```
NutThreadCreate("httpd0", HTTPService,  
               (void *) (uptr_t) i, NUT_THREAD_MAINSTACK);
```

A communication socket is then established by calling `NutTcpCreateSocket()`:

```
sock = NutTcpCreateSocket();
```

The HTTP service thread accepts the port 80 for communication:

```
NutTcpAccept(sock, 80);
```

We need to check if enough memory is available for the network buffer:

```
NutHeapAvailable()
```

To establish a HTTP server, we ask for a network buffer:

```
if ((stream = _fdopen((int) ((uptr_t) sock), "r+b")) != 0)  
{  
    NutHttpRequestProcessRequest(stream);  
    fclose(stream);  
}
```

The Nut/Net employs a dataflow method where data is pushed into the protocol layers just after data being received. The data is not buffered unless one of the layers is set to perform it. Data typically are then pushed into the socket. The procedure `NutHttpRequestProcessRequest()` request a network buffer for the HTTP process. At the end of connection, the socket should be terminated by calling the network API function `NutTcpCloseSocket(sock)`.

4.3.3 ADC Communication

To transmit the ADC data from the MAX1270 devices, we created a function called `ADCPackage()`. Using this function, the ADC data are retrieved using the ADC function `Read_ADC()` and are then streamed to a file on the HTTP server:

4.3. TAILORED HTTP SERVER APPLICATION

```
static int ADCPackage(FILE * stream, REQUEST * req)
{
    unsigned char s[4];
    unsigned int i = 0;
    unsigned int a1, a2, a3, a4;
    NutHttpSendHeaderTop(stream, req, 200, "Ok");
    NutHttpSendHeaderBot(stream, html_mt, -1);
    for (i = 0; i < 4000; i++)
    {
        a1 = Read_ADC(0, 0, ADC_HALFR_UNIP);
        a2 = Read_ADC(0, 1, ADC_HALFR_UNIP);
        a3 = Read_ADC(1, 0, ADC_HALFR_BIP);
        a4 = Read_ADC(1, 1, ADC_HALFR_BIP);
        _itoa(a1, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
        _itoa(a2, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
        _itoa(a3, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
        _itoa(a4, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
    }
    fflush(stream);
    return 0;
}
```

For use by a desktop program, the ADC data should stream to a file on the server. However, the integer format takes too long for a real-time transmission owing to the time required for writing to a file, so we utilize the `itoa()` function imported from the C runtime (CRT) library to convert integers into strings. Afterwards, the `stdio` function `fputs()` is used to send the string stream.

We register the function `ADCPackage()` as a common gateway interface (CGI) using the function `NutRegisterCgi()` inside the I/O stream routine `ADCCConnect()`:

```
static void ADCCConnect(FILE *stream)
{
    __asm__ volatile (
        " cli" "\n\t"
    );
    fprintf(stream, "Ready!\r\n");
    NutRegisterCgi("adc", ADCPackage);
    __asm__ volatile (
        " sei" "\n\t"
    );
}
```

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

```
);  
}
```

The ADC routine `ADCConnect()` is placed inside the TCP service thread.

The storage of ADC data takes place in the server station. The hardware that is necessary for sampling the data as well as time stamping it is included in both the ADC and Ethernut boards. The digitized information is delivered to a CGI on an HTTP server via the Ethernut across a TCP/IP network. When the data have been processed via HTTP, they are written to a file that takes roughly 2 seconds to save the data. The data transmitted in the final structure format can be used by a desktop program such as MATLAB. The MATLAB program changes the data such that it is in the standard data format known as the hexadecimal frame format that can be read by the `sscanf()` function in MATLAB.

4.4 MATLAB Program

The MATLAB program uses a 2KHz sampling rate for the channels in a frame file for data analysis. However, it takes time to download the frame file from an HTTP server and to convert the data into a MATLAB compatible hexadecimal frame format (see [34]). This issue can be resolved by employing the binary format in the future, but it currently has compatibility problems with MATLAB functions. The MATLAB function has access to the HTTP server for the most current virtual disk array data. The server listens on a TCP/IP port for incoming connections and stores the data array on the server. This port allows clients to connect to the server and seek data.

To establish a TCP/IP communication in MATLAB, we need to create a TCPIP object using the function `tcpip()` by specifying the remote host name and the remote port number. If the remote port is not given, 80 is employed. For example, the remote host `127.0.0.1` and the remote port `4012`:

```
t = tcpip('127.0.0.1',4012);
```

We can check the TCPIP object `t` with the command `whos`:

```
whos t
  Name      Size      Bytes Class
  t         1x1         640   tcpip object
```

Once, the TCPIP object `t` is created, we can connect to the host with the function `fopen(t)`. We first need to start the echo server and open a TCP/IP socket:

```
echotcpip('on',4012)
t = tcpip('127.0.0.1',4012);
fopen(t)
```

and then write to the host or read from it:

```
fwrite(t,65:74)
A = fread(t,10);
```

To disconnect from the host, we terminate our connection the TCPIP object `t` using the function `fclose(t)`:

```
fclose(t)
echotcpip('off')
```

We also stop the echo server.

To establish a UDP communication in MATLAB, we need to create a UDP object using the function `udp()` by specifying the given remote host and port number. For example, the host `127.0.0.1` and port `4012`:

```
u = udp('127.0.0.1',4012);
```

We can also verify the UDP object `u` using the command `whos`:

```
whos u
  Name      Size      Bytes Class
  u         1x1         632   udp object
```

Once, the UDP object `t` is made, we can connect to the host with the function `fopen(t)`. We again start the echo server and open a UDP socket:

```
echoudp('on',4012)
u = udp('127.0.0.1',4012);
fopen(u)
```

Then, writing to or reading from the host can be done:

```
fwrite(u,65:74)
A = fread(u,10);
```

We stop the echo server and use `fclose()` to disconnect the UDP object from

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

Figure 4.2: Diagram of communication between Nut/OS and MATLAB.

the host:

```
echoudp('off')
fclose(u)
```

To have a HTTP/FTP communication in MATLAB, we use the function `urlread()` to retrieve the contents of the URL of a HTTP/FTP server

```
s = urlread('ftp://127.0.0.1')
s = urlread('http://127.0.0.1')
```

and the function `urlwrite()` to store the contents of a URL into a file:

```
urlwrite('http://127.0.0.1', 'filename.dat')
```

The connection to our ADC system can be established in MATLAB through the IP address `192.168.0.170` in both the TCP socket and a web browser. We first need to start the echo server and create a TCP object:

```
echotcpip('on', 100);
t = tcpip('192.168.0.170', 100);
```

Then, we open the TCP object:

```
fopen(t);
```

Using `fscanf()`, we can have a hand-shake connection with our ADC system:

```
fscanf(t)
```


Figure 4.3: Data acquired by the ADC system and transferred via Ethernet along with test signals plotted in MATLAB.

To retrieve the data, we read the following URL with `urlread()`:

```
s = urlread('http://192.168.0.170/cgi-bin/adc');
```

At the end of connection, we close the socket and stop the echo server:

```
fclose(t);
echotcpip('off');
```

The connection between Nut/OS and MATLAB can be established via port 100 (TCP) and 80 (HTTP). It is asked for the data by scanning port 100 and receives it on the HTTP server or port 80 (see Fig. 4.2).

After the data is written in the HEX string format into the server, the routine `sscanf()` can easily obtain them in MATLAB:

```
A = sscanf(s, '%x');
```

We also need to adjust the data based on the voltage reference in each channel:

```
for k = 1:2
    a(k,i) = 5*A(4*(i-1)+k)/4095;
end
for k = 3:4
    a(k,i) = A(4*(i-1)+k);
    if a(k,i) >= 2048
        a(k,i) = -(4095 - a(k,i));
    end
end
```

4. NUT/OS AND ADC DEVICE DRIVER

```
    end
    a(k,i) = 5*a(k,i)/2047;
end
```

The information of all the four channels are displayed using the function `plot()`:

```
echotcpip('on',100);
t = tcpip('192.168.0.170',100);
fopen(t);
fscanf(t)
s = urlread('http://192.168.0.170/cgi-bin/adc');
fclose(t);
echotcpip('off');
A = sscanf(s,'%x');
for i = 1:4000
    for k = 1:2
        a(k,i) = 5*A(4*(i-1)+k)/4095;
    end
    for k = 3:4
        a(k,i)=A(4*(i-1)+k);
        if a(k,i)>=2048
            a(k,i)=-(4095-a(k,i));
        end
        a(k,i) = 5*a(k,i)/2047;
    end
end
end
t = 0.0007:0.0007:2.8;
subplot(4,1,1); plot(t,a(1,:));
subplot(4,1,2); plot(t,a(2,:));
subplot(4,1,3); plot(t,a(3,:));
subplot(4,1,4); plot(t,a(4,:));
```

The Ethernut server can send data at the full sampling rate. We send the data to MATLAB, since this program is widely used in the analysis of neuromuscular blockade data. The routine `urlread()` in MATLAB can read files that are on the local server storage of an Ethernut. To get data from a server, we use `tcpip('192.168.0.170',100)` to run the client program on port 100. The client can retrieve data at the full sampling rate, as well as data on trends and calibration data in MATLAB codes. For monitoring data, we simply plot them in MATLAB (see Fig. 4.3).

5

Conclusions

In this project, we have designed and built a new analog-to-digital converter (ADC) circuit board (see Chapter 3) coupled with an embedded Ethernet device called *Ethernut* (Chapter 2) as a data acquisition (DAQ) system for this purpose. Moreover, we have developed a device driver program for our ADC system in order to work as a CGI in a local web server via HTTP and TCP protocols on the real-time operating system *Nut/OS* of the Ethernut-based DAQ system (see Chapter 4). The aim of the DAQ system and our ADC unit is to provide a way to measure and record the neuromuscular blockades of patients under anesthesia. The Ethernet-enabled device can get sensor data from the ADC system and set up a local server so that the data can be transmitted to a desktop computer, where they can be displayed using a graphical user interface. Based on our results, the Ethernut system, which is connected to the ADC, works well and can reliably transmit data in real time. However, there are a number of problems and limitations that should be resolved in the future.

The main problem is that the AVR microcontroller on the Ethernut board has some hardware limitations. RAM space restricts the number of samples that can be processed at any given moment. Moreover, the ATmega128 microcontroller can only perform 16 million instructions per second (MIPS). With high-bandwidth sensor data, however, speed becomes a limiting factor for real-

5. CONCLUSIONS

time transmission. This means that the Ethernut system is not suitable for high-speed real-time data streaming. Cascaded networking, on the other hand, may be able to solve this problem and handle data at an acceptable rate. However, it is not a big issue for sensor data with a low bandwidth, and it may be resolvable for data with a higher bandwidth if on-board processing is done to reduce the quantity of data before transmission.

In the future, the data will need to be stored in binary format on the HTTP server, instead of the currently used hexadecimal frame format, and some codes will need to be developed to retrieve the binary data from the HTTP server. The program should be able to receive the data and convert them to a readable format. C-MEX, MATLAB *executable* in C language, can accomplish this task for both Simulink and the M-file in MATLAB. Moreover, MATLAB has some features for extracting data from a URL using a Java script, which must be considered in the future. Under the condition of using the binary format, the sampling rate can reach up to 4 or 5 kHz. With the ATmega128 microcontroller limited to 16 MIPS, we can solve the instruction performance issue. There is also the option of using memory to solve the performance issue. Nevertheless, the RAM size limitation prevents it. Although writing the binary image of data to a file in HTTP Server increases the sampling rate, we need to develop C-MEX code in MATLAB to retrieve and unpack the binary data.

The Ethernut-based system gathers data from the EMG, MMG, and AMG sensors that are attached to our MAX1270-based ADC circuit (see Appendix A), packages them, and stores them in its local web server so that a computer can use them in real time. It meets all of the requirements discussed in Chapter 2, as well as low cost, low energy consumption, and small dimensions. On a desktop or laptop computer, we can perform some statistics to validate data directly downloaded from the server in real time. Even though all testing is conducted with very low bandwidth data (only a few hundred samples per second), the system should be able to handle data rates of up to 4096 samples per second

without any problems. To support data at a higher bandwidth, the system needs to be expanded with additional hardware devices, mostly RAM.

There are some additional improvements that would increase the functionality of the Ethernet system. For example, we can prepare a new, smaller printed circuit board for the ADC system instead of our current PCB (see Appendix B). We can also make additional ADC modules that allow the connection of more sensors to the Ethernet system. Once completed, these additions could serve as the basis for a robust controller system for neuromuscular blockades and other sophisticated applications in anesthesia control. Our monitoring system is less expensive than currently available commercial devices for anesthesia monitoring. However, we need to develop some fault-finding algorithms on both the embedded system and the desktop computer to ensure the accuracy of transmitted data.

The Ethernet embedded system, along with our ADC system for monitoring EMG, MMG, and AMG signals that were designed and developed as part of this project, have all the features required for anesthesia monitoring and control. It can be used as the base for a more advanced data acquisition system in the future that could be capable of practical measurements of neuromuscular blockades in patients under anesthesia for clinical purposes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

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Appendix A

Schematic Circuit Diagram

APPENDIX A. SCHEMATIC CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Size:	A3			Universität Rostock		
Engineer:	A. Danehkar		Date:	7/31/2007 07:25:35a		
Checked:			Approved:			
Description:	ADC Board				Page:	1/1
Filename:	sch13				Revision:	1.0

Size: A3	Universität Rostock		
Engineers:	A. Danehkar	Dates:	7/31/2007 07:29:35
Checked:		Approved:	
Description:	ADC Board	Pages:	1/1
Filename:	sch13	Revisions:	1.0

Figure A.1: The Schematic Circuit Diagram of our ADC System.

Appendix B

Printed Circuit Board

APPENDIX B. PRINTED CIRCUIT BOARD

PCB: All Layers

PCB: Element Labels

Figure B.1: The Printed Circuit Board of our ADC System.

PCB: Top Layer

PCB: Mirror Bottom Layer

PCB: Pads and Keep-outs

PCB: Drill Holes

Appendix C

Data Sheet

Multirange, +5V, 8-Channel, Serial 12-Bit ADCs

MAX1270/MAX1271

Table 1. Control-Byte Format

BIT 7 (MSB)	BIT 6	BIT 5	BIT 4	BIT 3	BIT 2	BIT 1	BIT 0 (LSB)
START	SEL2	SEL1	SEL0	RNG	BIP	PD1	PD0
BIT	NAME	DESCRIPTION					
7 (MSB)	START	First logic 1 after \overline{CS} goes low defines the beginning of the control byte.					
6, 5, 4	SEL2, SEL1, SEL0	These 3 bits select the desired "on" channel (Table 2).					
3	RNG	Selects the full-scale input voltage range (Table 3).					
2	BIP	Selects the unipolar or bipolar conversion mode (Table 3).					
1, 0 (LSB)	PD1, PD0	Select clock and power-down modes (Table 4).					

Table 2. Channel Selection

SEL2	SEL1	SEL0	CHANNEL
0	0	0	CH0
0	0	1	CH1
0	1	0	CH2
0	1	1	CH3
1	0	0	CH4
1	0	1	CH5
1	1	0	CH6
1	1	1	CH7

Table 4. Power-Down and Clock Selection

PD1	PD0	MODE
0	0	Normal operation (always on), internal clock mode.
0	1	Normal operation (always on), external clock mode.
1	0	Standby power-down mode (STBYPD), clock mode unaffected.
1	1	Full power-down mode (FULLPD), clock mode unaffected.

Table 3. Range and Polarity Selection for MAX1270/MAX1271

RANGE AND POLARITY SELECTION FOR THE MAX1270					
INPUT RANGE	RNG	BIP	Negative FULL SCALE	ZERO SCALE (V)	FULL SCALE
0 to +5V	0	0	—	0	$V_{REF} \times 1.2207$
0 to +10V	1	0	—	0	$V_{REF} \times 2.4414$
±5V	0	1	$-V_{REF} \times 1.2207$	0	$V_{REF} \times 1.2207$
±10V	1	1	$-V_{REF} \times 2.4414$	0	$V_{REF} \times 2.4414$
RANGE AND POLARITY SELECTION FOR THE MAX1271					
INPUT RANGE	RNG	BIP	Negative FULL SCALE	ZERO SCALE (V)	FULL SCALE
0 to $V_{REF}/2$	0	0	—	0	$V_{REF}/2$
0 to V_{REF}	1	0	—	0	V_{REF}
± $V_{REF}/2$	0	1	$-V_{REF}/2$	0	$V_{REF}/2$
± V_{REF}	1	1	$-V_{REF}$	0	V_{REF}

Figure C.1: MAX1270/MAX1271 Programmable Register [20].

Appendix D

Glossary

ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
AMG	acceleromyography
API	Application Programming Interface
ARP	Address Resolution Protocol
CGI	Common Gateway Interface
CMOS	Complementary Metal-Oxide Semiconductor
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAQ	Data Acquisition System
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DNS	Domain Name System
EAGLE	Easily Applicable Graphical Layout Editor
ECAD	Electronic Computer-Aided Design
EEG	Electroencephalogramm
EEPROM	electrically erasable programmable read-only memory
EMG	Electromyography
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
FT	Fourier Transform
HTML	HyperText Markup Language

APPENDIX D. GLOSSARY

HTTP	HyperText Transport Protocol
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
I ² C	Inter-Integrated Circuit
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IP	Internet Protocol
JTAG	Joint Test Action Group
LSB	Least Significant Bit
MSB	Most Significant Bit
MMG	Mechanomyography
MISO	Master in/Slave Out
MOSI	Master Out/Slave In
PPP	Point-to-Point Protocol
PHP	PHP Hypertext Preprocessor
RAM	Random-Access Memory
ROM	Read-Only Memory
SCK	Serial Clock
SCLK	Serial Clock
SNTP	Simple Network Time Protocol
SPCR	SPI Control Register
SPDR	SPI Data Register
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface
SPSR	SPI Status Register
SRAM	Static Random-Access Memory
SS	Slave Select
TCI	Target Controlled Infusion System
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TFTP	Trivial File Transfer Protocol
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Appendix E

Supplementary Material

The supplemental compact disc (CD) includes a folder (`src`) containing the codes required for this microcontroller-based measurement system. There are the code `httpserv.c` modified for establishing a HTTP server with TCP sockets to communicate between ADC and PC: `\src\httpd\httpserv.c`. It has a `Makefile` needed for compiling the codes (`\src\httpd\Makefile`). The `urom.c` code is the default HTTP ROM program (`\src\httpd\urom.c`). The MAX1270 device driver, `max1270.c` and `max1270.h`, which was developed in the project, are also included (`\src\httpd\max1270.c` and `\src\httpd\max1270.h`). The HTML file (`index.html`) is for displaying the home page of the HTTP server on a web browser. There are kernel and network files for NUT/OS and other libraries by egnite Software GmbH for the Ethernut board (`\src\ethernut-4.2.1`). A simple MATLAB code (`\matlab\adc2pc.m`) is also included, which was written in this project for monitoring and plotting the ADC data from the Ethernut DAQ. The schematic circuit diagram (`adc.sch`) and the printed circuit board (PCB; `adc.brđ`) of the ADC system designed with CadSoft GmbH's EAGLE v4.16r1 in this project are also in a different folder (`doc`) in the supplement CD, along with the data sheets of MAX1270, LT1079, ADUM1201, ADUM2401, and TEL 3-1223 used on our ADC board, as well as the data sheets of ATmega128 and LAN91C111 used by the Ethernut board v2.1 and the Ethernut documentation.

E.1 Installation and Configuration

We use the following hardware tools for this project:

- A computer with Microsoft Windows XP operating system,
- An Ethernut Board v2.1 with an ATmega128 μ controller,
- A STK5000-JTAG plug for programming ATmega128,
- our ADC circuit board designed using two MAX1270 ICs,

and the following software tools:

- Open-source program WinAVR-GCC v20060125 for Windows, (alternatively, commercial program ImageCraft ICCAVR IDE v7)
- Nut/OS v4.2.1 for Ethernut v2.1b, available on the Ethernut CD,
- AVR Studio v4.12.0.460, available from the Atmel website,
- MathWorks MATLAB v7.2 2006a for Windows.

All these software packages are available in the supplement CD of this project. We first install AVR Studio, then WinAVR-GCC and Nut/OS. WinAVR is a suite of GNU Compiler Collection (GCC) tools for programming AVR microcontrollers.

Nut/OS Configuration

Nut/OS can be set to use for a specific compiler, a target microcontroller, and network options. To configure Nut/OS, we run the Nut/OS Configurator:

and select a configuration file (ethernut21b.conf for the Ethernut 2.1 rev. b).

From the menu, we choose Edit → Settings to show the NutConf Settings:

On the Tool tab of the NutConf Settings Dialog, we specify the location, where contains the AVR-GCC bin directory, followed by other necessary libraries:

The last tab is reserved for giving the location of sample projects.

In the building tree on the main window, we need to select the compiler (GCC for AVR, or ImageCraft for AVR if ICCAVR used) and target processor (Atmel ATmega128). We also need to deselect any other incorrect compilers and microcontrollers.

After the configuration, we can now compile Nut/OS libraries.

Compiling Nut/OS Libraries

The Nut/OS installation includes a set of pre-build libraries for different types of Ethernet boards located in the path `nut/lib/gcc`. To build the Nut/OS libraries, we select `Build` → `Build Nut/OS` on the menu. Then, the Configurator creates the build directory if it does not exist or updates an existing one. It produces necessary Makefiles for compiling the project, and some C header files in the path `include/cfg`. They are tailored for specific hardware requirements. After a successful build of the Nut/OS libraries, some AVR libraries and object files are created. We can now use the Configurator to make an application directory for our purpose and copy some demo projects into this directory. by choosing `Build` → `Create Sample Directory` from the menu.

Compiling a Nut/OS Application

The build of a project is done in two steps. First, we choose `Build` → `Generate Build Tree` from the menu, which requests the configuration tool to prepare a new building directory or modify an existing one in the building path

specified in the settings. It creates a set of files including some C language header files in a folder called `include/cfg`. These files are from the Nut/OS source code, which can be tailored for a specific hardware. Finally, we select Build → Build Nut/OS from the menu, which requests the Configurator to run `make clean`, `make all`, and finally `make install`. The last step creates the AVR libraries, namely C runtime support library (`libnutcrt.a`), C runtime support library with floating point (`libnutcrtf.a`), device driver library (`libnutdev.a`), file system library (`libnutfs.a`), network library (`libnutnet.a`), RTOS kernel library (`libnutos.a`), protocol library (`libnutpro.a`), and RTOS initialization (`nutinit.o`). If it fails, we should try to manually build in a terminal. We need to open a DOS terminal in the build directory and specify the path of the Nut/OS tools in the `PATH` environment.

```
set PATH=c:\ethernut-4.2.1\nut\tools\win32;%PATH%
```

Depending on the compiler, we also need to include the AVR-GCC path:

```
set PATH=c:\avrgcc\bin;c:\avrgcc\utils\bin;%PATH%
```

To manually build, we need to enter in a DOS terminal:

```
make clean
make install
```

Then, we should see some any error messages if the build is successful

Creating a Nut/OS Application

To create an application, we select Build → Create Sample Directory from the Configurator's menu, which creates a new or update an existing application. By default, Nut/OS employs DHCP to automatically install the TCP/IP settings. Even without DHCP, applications have these settings in the on-chip EEPROM, so they may not need any modifications. For this project, we modify the file `httpd/httpserv.c` included in the sample directory of Nut/OS. We change the IP address and the IP mask to fit the network environment of our Ethernut board. We may also need to change the MAC address to the one used in the

Ethernut Board. For other applications without MAC address, we should make sure that the address is unique on our local network.

While the Nut/OS Configurator creates a sample directory, it also adds a user configuration file with default settings for the Ethernut boards, in the other words, for boards equipped with the LAN91C111 Ethernet controller. If the board has with a different Ethernet controller, we need to correct it in the file `UserConf.mk` in the sample directory. When we recreate the sample directory in the same path, which overwrites all changes, but no changes in `UserConf.mk`.

Finally, we connect the programming adapter to the Ethernut board and the computer, and we compile our server application:

```
make clean
make all
make burn
```

It creates the binary file `httpserv.hex` in the Intel HEX file format, and the final command uploads the binary into our Ethernut board.

Programming the AVR Microcontroller

To upload the server application, we attach the AVR JTAG ICE to the Ethernut board, and the serial port of the JTAG ICE to one of the serial ports of the computer. We should switch off the power supply before any connection or disconnection of the JTAG cable, but we do not require switching off the power supply for connecting or disconnecting the RS232 port or the Ethernet cable. We turn on the 12-V power supply of the Ethernut Board. We then start AVR Studio and choose Tools → Program AVR → Connect from the menu. We choose the programming adapter JTAG ICE mkII on the AVR programmer selection dialog:

We then click on the Connect button to open the JTAG ICE mkII dialog:

We choose ATmega128 as a device and then click on the Read button in the Advanced tab. This causes that the device signature is read from the target board and shown in the signature field. If it is successful and the signature of the chosen device is matched, we can now upload our application into the FLASH memory of the Ethernet Board by switching to the Program tab. In the Flash section of the Program tab, we need to specify the input HEX file by navigating to our `httpd` directory in our application directory and selecting the file named `httpserv.hex`. We then press the Program button in the Flash section on the Program tab. AVR Studio will erase the ATmega FLASH memory and the HEX file is written into it and verify the result.

E.2 Tailored HTTP Server Program

We employed the programming tool provided by the Atmel AVR Studio for uploading the tailored HTTP server program (`httpd`) into the target hardware. The debug of our program was done using the COM1 serial port in a terminal emulator. The messages can be sent by `printf()` into the RS-232 port of a desktop computer. For example:

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
// Initialize the uart device.
NutRegisterDevice(&DEV_DEBUG, 0, 0);
freopen(DEV_DEBUG_NAME, "w", stdout);
_ioctl1(_fileno(stdout), UART_SETSPEED, &baud);
NutSleep(200);
printf("\n\nNut/OS %s HTTP Daemon...", NutVersionString());
```

We connected the Ethernut's RS232 to a serial port of our computer, and then started our terminal emulator (HyperTerminal) to view debugging outputs. In the terminal emulator, we utilized 115200 Baud, 8 data bits, 1 stop bit, no parity and no handshake:

We can also open the Ethernut IP address in a web browser and check the outputs. While the web browser gets the information, additional outputs may also be transferred via the RS232 serial port by the Ethernut device:

```
// Open a socket.
sock = NutTcpCreateSocket();
NutTcpAccept(sock, 80);
printf("[%u] Connected, %u bytes free\n", id,
...
// Close our socket.
NutTcpCloseSocket(sock);
printf("[%u] Disconnected\n", id);
```

Code E.1: `httpserv.c` of Nut/OS modified for communication with ADC.

```
/* Copyright (C) 2001-2004 by egnite Software GmbH. All rights
 * reserved.
 * Redistribution and use in source and binary forms, with or without
 * modification, are permitted provided that the following conditions
 * are met:
 * 1. Redistributions of source code must retain the above copyright
 * notice, this list of conditions and the following disclaimer.
 * 2. Redistributions in binary form must reproduce the above
 * copyright notice, this list of conditions and the following
 * disclaimer in the documentation and/or other materials provided
 * with the distribution.
 * 3. Neither the name of the copyright holders nor the names of
 * contributors may be used to endorse or promote products derived
 * from this software without specific prior written permission.
```

E.2. TAILORED HTTP SERVER PROGRAM

```
*
* Revision 1.15 2006/09/07 09:01:36 haraldkipp
* For additional information see http://www.ethernut.de/
*
* \example httpd/httserv.c
* Simple multithreaded HTTP daemon. */

/*! Modified by Ashkbiz Danehkar (University of Rostock, 2007).
* Summary of Changes:
* - MAX1270 Device Driver added,
* - itoa() imported from the CRT library,
* - ADCPackage() and ADCConnect() added,
* - set to work with TCP and HTTP services,
* - ADCConnect() added to the TCP service. */

/* Unique MAC address of the Ethernut Board.
* Ignored if EEPROM contains a valid configuration. */
#define MY_MAC "\x00\x06\x98\x30\x00\x35"
/* Unique IP address of the Ethernut Board.
* Ignored if DHCP is used. */
#define MY_IPADDR "192.168.192.35"
/* IP network mask of the Ethernut Board.
* Ignored if DHCP is used. */
#define MY_IPMASK "255.255.255.0"
/* Gateway IP address for the Ethernut Board.
* Ignored if DHCP is used. */
#define MY_IPGATE "192.168.192.1"
/* ICCAVR Demo is limited. Try to use the bare minimum. */

#if !defined(__IMAGECRAFT__)
/* Wether we should use DHCP. */
#define USE_DHCP
/* Wether we should run a discovery responder. */
#define USE_DISCOVERY
/* Wether to use PHAT file system. */
// #define USE_PHAT
#endif /* __IMAGECRAFT__ */

#ifdef USE_PHAT
#if defined(ETHERNUT3)
/* Ethernut 3 file system. */
#define MY_FSDEV devPhat0
#define MY_FSDEV_NAME "PHAT0"
/* Ethernut 3 block device interface. */
#define MY_BLKDEV devNplMmc0
#define MY_BLKDEV_NAME "MMC0"
#elif defined(AT91SAM7X_EK)
/* SAM7X-EK file system. */
#define MY_FSDEV devPhat0
#define MY_FSDEV_NAME "PHAT0"
/* SAM7X-EK block device interface. */
#define MY_BLKDEV devAt91SpiMmc0
```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
#define MY_BLKDEV_NAME "MMC0"
#elif defined(AT91SAM9260_EK)
/* SAM9260-EK file system. */
#define MY_FSDEV devPhat0
#define MY_FSDEV_NAME "PHAT0"
/* SAM9260-EK block device interface. */
#define MY_BLKDEV devAt91Mci0
#define MY_BLKDEV_NAME "MCI0"
#endif
#endif /* USE_PHAT */

#ifndef MY_FSDEV
#define MY_FSDEV devUrom
#endif

#ifdef MY_FSDEV_NAME
#define MY_HTTPROOT MY_FSDEV_NAME "/"
#endif

#include <cfg/os.h>
#include <cfg/arch.h>
#include <string.h>
#include <stdio.h>
#include <io.h>
#include <fcntl.h>
#include <dev/board.h>
#include <dev/urom.h>
#include <dev/nplmmc.h>
#include <dev/sbimmc.h>
#include <fs/phatfs.h>
#include <sys/version.h>
#include <sys/thread.h>
#include <sys/timer.h>
#include <sys/event.h>
#include <sys/heap.h>
#include <sys/confnet.h>
#include <sys/socket.h>
#include <arpa/inet.h>
#include <net/route.h>
#include <pro/httpd.h>
#include <pro/dhcp.h>
#include <pro/ssi.h>
#include <pro/asp.h>
#include <pro/discover.h>

#include "max1270.h" // Added by AD 2007

#ifdef NUTDEBUG
#include <sys/osdebug.h>
#include <net/netdebug.h>
#endif
static char *html_mt = "text/html";
```

E.2. TAILORED HTTP SERVER PROGRAM

```
/* *****  
/* ASPCallback */  
/* */  
/* This routine must have been registered by */  
/* NutRegisterAspCallback() and is automatically called by */  
/* NutHttpRequestProcessFileRequest() when the server process a page */  
/* with an asp function. */  
/* */  
/* Return 0 on success, -1 otherwise. */  
/* *****  
static int ASPCallback (char *pASPFunction, FILE *stream)  
{  
    if (strcmp(pASPFunction, "usr_date") == 0)  
    {  
        fprintf(stream, "Dummy example: 01.01.2005");  
        return(0);  
    }  
    if (strcmp(pASPFunction, "usr_time") == 0)  
    {  
        fprintf(stream, "Dummy example: 12:15:02");  
        return(0);  
    }  
    return (-1);  
}  
/*! \fn Service(void *arg)  
* \brief HTTP service thread.  
*  
* The endless loop in this thread waits for a client connect,  
* processes the HTTP request and disconnects. Nut/Net doesn't  
* support a server backlog. If one client has established a  
* connection, further connect attempts will be rejected.  
* Typically browsers open more than one connection in order  
* to load images concurrently. So we run this routine by  
* several threads.  
*  
*/  
THREAD(HTTPService, arg)  
{  
    TCPSOCKET *sock;  
    FILE *stream;  
    u_char id = (u_char) ((uptr_t) arg);  
    NutThreadSetPriority(253);  
    /* Now loop endless for connections. */  
    for (;;)   
    {  
        /* Create a socket. */  
        if ((sock = NutTcpCreateSocket()) == 0)  
        {  
            printf("[%u] Creating HTTP socket failed\n", id);  
            NutSleep(5000);  
            continue;  
        }  
    }  
}
```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
    /* Listen on port 80. This call will block
     * until we get a connection from a client. */
    NutTcpAccept(sock, 80);
#if defined(__AVR__)
    printf("[%u] HTTP Connected, %u bytes free\n", id,
           NutHeapAvailable());
#else
    printf("[%u] HTTP Connected, %lu bytes free\n", id,
           NutHeapAvailable());
#endif
    /* Wait until at least 8 kByte of free RAM is available.
     * This will keep the client connected in low memory
     * situations. */
#if defined(__AVR__)
    while (NutHeapAvailable() < 8192)
    {
#else
    while (NutHeapAvailable() < 4096)
    {
#endif
    printf("[%u] Low mem\n", id);
    NutSleep(1000);
    }
    /* Associate a stream with the socket so we can use standard
     * I/O calls. */
    if ((stream = _fdopen((int) ((uptr_t) sock), "r+b")) == 0)
    {
        printf("[%u] Creating stream device failed\n", id);
    }
    else
    {
        /* This API call saves us a lot of work. It will parse the
         * client's HTTP request, send any requested file from the
         * registered file system or handle CGI requests by calling
         * our registered CGI routine. */
        NutHttpProcessRequest(stream);
        /* Destroy the virtual stream device. */
        fclose(stream);
    }
    /* Close our socket. */
    NutTcpCloseSocket(sock);
    printf("[%u] HTTP Disconnected\n", id);
}
}
// itoa code from the C runtime (CRT) library: AD 2007
#define radix 16
char *_itoa(int val, char *buf)
{
    char *p;
    char *firstdig;
    char temp;
    unsigned digval;
```

```

p = buf;
// Save pointer to first digit
firstdig = p;
do
{
    digval = (unsigned) (val % radix);
    val /= radix;
    // Convert to ascii and store
    if (digval > 9)
        *p++ = (char) (digval - 10 + 'a');
    else
        *p++ = (char) (digval + '0');
} while (val > 0);
// We now have the digit of the number in the buffer, but in
reverse
// order. Thus we reverse them now.
*p-- = '\0';
do
{
    temp = *p;
    *p = *firstdig;
    *firstdig = temp;
    p--;
    firstdig++;
} while (firstdig < p);
return buf;
}

// ADCPackage by AD 2007 for communication with the ADC
#define SAMPLE_NUM 4000
static int ADCPackage(FILE * stream, REQUEST * req)
{
    unsigned char s[4];
    unsigned int i = 0;
    unsigned int a1, a2, a3, a4;
    NutHttpSendHeaderTop(stream, req, 200, "Ok");
    NutHttpSendHeaderBot(stream, html_mt, -1);
    for (i = 0; i < SAMPLE_NUM; i++)
    {
        a1 = Read_ADC(0, 0, ADC_HALFR_UNIP);
        a2 = Read_ADC(0, 1, ADC_HALFR_UNIP);
        a3 = Read_ADC(1, 0, ADC_HALFR_BIP);
        a4 = Read_ADC(1, 1, ADC_HALFR_BIP);
        //delay_us(150);
        _itoa(a1, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
        _itoa(a2, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
        _itoa(a3, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
    }
}

```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
        fputs(" ", stream);
        _itoa(a4, s);
        fputs(s, stream);
        fputs(" ", stream);
    }
    fflush(stream);
    return 0;
}

// ADCCConnect by AD 2007 for connection to the ADC
static void ADCCConnect(FILE *stream)
{
    __asm__ volatile (
        " cli" "\n\t"
    );
    fprintf(stream, "Ready!\r\n");
    NutRegisterCgi("adc", ADCPackage);
    __asm__ volatile (
        " sei" "\n\t"
    );
}

/*! \fn Service(void *arg)
 * \brief TCP service thread.
 *
 * The endless loop in this thread waits for a client connect,
 * processes the HTTP request and disconnects. Nut/Net doesn't
 * support a server backlog. If one client has established a
 * connection, further connect attempts will be rejected.
 * Typically browsers open more than one connection in order
 * to load images concurrently. So we run this routine by
 * several threads.
 */
THREAD(TCPService, arg)
{
    TCPSOCKET *sock;
    FILE *stream;
    u_char id = (u_char) ((uptr_t) arg);
    NutThreadSetPriority(32);
    /* Now loop endless for connections. */
    for (;;)
    {
        /* Create a socket.*/
        if ((sock = NutTcpCreateSocket()) == 0)
        {
            printf("[%u] Creating TCP socket failed\n", id);
            NutSleep(5000);
            continue;
        }
        /* Listen on port 100. This call will block
         * until we get a connection
        */
    }
}
```

E.2. TAILORED HTTP SERVER PROGRAM

```
    * from a client. */
    NutTcpAccept(sock, 100);
#if defined(__AVR__)
    printf("[%u] TCP Connected, %u bytes free\n", id,
        NutHeapAvailable());
#else
    printf("[%u] TCP Connected, %lu bytes free\n", id,
        NutHeapAvailable());
#endif
    /* Wait until at least 8 kByte of free RAM is available.
     * This will
     * keep the client connected in low memory situations. */
#if defined(__AVR__)
    while (NutHeapAvailable() < 8192)
    {
#else
    while (NutHeapAvailable() < 4096)
    {
#endif
        printf("[%u] Low mem\n", id);
        NutSleep(1000);
    }
    /* Associate a stream with the socket so we can
     * use standard I/O calls. */
    if ((stream = _fdopen((int) ((uptr_t) sock), "r+b")) == 0)
    {
        printf("[%u] Creating stream device failed\n", id);
    }
    else
    {
        /* This API call saves us a lot of work. It will parse the
         * client's HTTP request, send any requested file from the
         * registered file system or handle CGI requests by calling
         * our registered CGI routine. */
        //NutHttpProcessRequest(stream);
        ADCCConnect(stream); // added by AD 2007
        /* Destroy the virtual stream device. */
        fclose(stream);
    }
    /* Close our socket. */
    NutTcpCloseSocket(sock);
    printf("[%u] TCP Disconnected\n", id);
}
}
/*!
 * \brief Main application routine.
 *
 * Nut/OS automatically calls this entry after initialization.
 */
int main(void)
{
    u_long baud = 115200;
```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
u_char i;

Port_Init(); // Added by AD 2007
SPI_Init(); // Added by AD 2007

/* Initialize the uart device. */
NutRegisterDevice(&DEV_DEBUG, 0, 0);
freopen(DEV_DEBUG_NAME, "w", stdout);
_ioctl(_fileno(stdout), UART_SETSPEED, &baud);
NutSleep(200);
printf("\n\nNut/OS %s HTTP Daemon...", NutVersionString());

#ifdef NUTDEBUG
NutTraceTcp(stdout, 0);
NutTraceOs(stdout, 0);
NutTraceHeap(stdout, 0);
NutTracePPP(stdout, 0);
#endif

/* Register Ethernet controller. */
if (NutRegisterDevice(&DEV_ETHER, 0, 0))
{
    puts("Registering device failed");
}
printf("Configure %s...", DEV_ETHER_NAME);
if (NutNetLoadConfig(DEV_ETHER_NAME))
{
    u_char mac[] = MY_MAC;
    printf("initial boot...");
#ifdef USE_DHCP
    if (NutDhcpIfConfig(DEV_ETHER_NAME, mac, 60000))
#endif
    {
        u_long ip_addr = inet_addr(MY_IPADDR);
        u_long ip_mask = inet_addr(MY_IPMASK);
        u_long ip_gate = inet_addr(MY_IPGATE);
        printf("No DHCP...");
        if (NutNetIfConfig(DEV_ETHER_NAME, mac,
            ip_addr, ip_mask) == 0)
        {
            /* Without DHCP we had to set the default
            gateway manually.*/
            if(ip_gate)
            {
                printf("hard coded gate...");
                NutIpRouteAdd(0, 0, ip_gate, &DEV_ETHER);
            }
            puts("OK");
        }
        else
        {
            puts("failed");
        }
    }
}
```

E.2. TAILORED HTTP SERVER PROGRAM

```
    }
  }
}
else
{
#ifdef USE_DHCP
  if (NutDhcpIfConfig(DEV_ETHER_NAME, 0, 60000))
  {
    puts("failed");
  }
  else
  {
    puts("OK");
  }
#else
  if (NutNetIfConfig(DEV_ETHER_NAME, 0, 0, confnet.cdn_ip_mask))
  {
    puts("failed");
  }
  else
  {
    puts("OK");
  }
#endif
}
printf("%s ready\n", inet_ntoa(confnet.cdn_ip_addr));

#ifdef USE_DISCOVERY
  NutRegisterDiscovery((u_long)-1, 0, DISF_INITIAL_ANN);
#endif

/* Register our device for the file system. */
NutRegisterDevice(&MY_FSDEV, 0, 0);

#ifdef MY_BLKDEV
/* Register block device. */
printf("Registering block device ' " MY_BLKDEV_NAME "'...");
if (NutRegisterDevice(&MY_BLKDEV, 0, 0))
{
  puts("failed");
  for (;;)
}
puts("OK");

/* Mount partition. */
printf("Mounting block device ' "
      MY_BLKDEV_NAME ":1/" MY_FSDEV_NAME "'...");
if (_open(MY_BLKDEV_NAME ":1/" MY_FSDEV_NAME,
          O_RDWR | _O_BINARY) == -1)
{
  puts("failed");
  for (;;)

```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
    }
    puts("OK");
#endif

#ifdef MY_HTTPROOT
    /* Register root path. */
    printf("Registering HTTP root ' " MY_HTTPROOT "' ...");
    if (NutRegisterHttpRoot(MY_HTTPROOT))
    {
        puts("failed");
        for (;;)
        }
    puts("OK");
#endif

    /* Register SSI and ASP handler */
    NutRegisterSsi();
    NutRegisterAsp();
    NutRegisterAspCallback(ASPCallback);

    /* Start four server threads. */
    //for (i = 1; i <= 4; i++)
    //{
    i=1;
    char *thname1 = "httpd0";
    thname1[5] = '0' + i;
    NutThreadCreate(thname1, HTTPService,
        (void *) (uptr_t) i, NUT_THREAD_MAINSTACK);
    //}
    char *thname2 = "tcpadc";
    NutThreadCreate(thname2, TCPService, NULL, NUT_THREAD_MAINSTACK);
    /* We could do something useful here, like serving a watchdog. */
    NutThreadSetPriority(254);
    for (;;)
    {
        NutSleep(60000);
    }
}
```

E.3 MAX1270 Device Driver

Code E.2: max1270.h developed for supporting MAX1270 on Nut/OS.

```
#ifndef _MAX1270_H_
#define _MAX1270_H_
/*!
 * Written by Ashkbiz Danekar (University of Rostock, 2007)
 * for supporting MAX1270 device on Nut/OS.
 */
```

```

/ * !
 * \file max1270.h
 * \brief MAX1270 definitions.
 */

/ * !
 * \addtogroup xgMAX1270
 */
/ * @ { */

// Power-Down and Clock Selection
#define ADC_NORMP_INTCLK 0x00
#define ADC_NORMP_EXTCLK 0x01
#define ADC_STBYPD      0x02
#define ADC_FULLLPD     0x03

// Range and Polarity Selection
#define ADC_HALFR_UNIP 0x00<<2
#define ADC_HALFR_BIP 0x01<<2
#define ADC_FULLLR_UNIP 0x02<<2
#define ADC_FULLLR_BIP 0x03<<2

/ * @ } */

extern void delay_us(unsigned int microseconds);
extern void delay_ms(unsigned int time_ms);

extern void Port_Init(void);

extern void SPI_Init(void);
extern void SPITransmit( unsigned char data );
extern unsigned char SPIReceive( unsigned char data );

extern unsigned int Read_ADC(unsigned char num, unsigned char
    channel, unsigned char rang_polar);

#endif

```

Code E.3: max1270.c developed for supporting MAX1270 on Nut/OS.

```

/ * !
 * Written by Ashkbiz Danehkar (University of Rostock, 2007)
 * for supporting MAX1270 device on Nut/OS.
 */
/ * !
 * \file max1270.c
 * \brief MAX1270 routines.
 *
 * This module provides MAX1270 read/write routines.
 */

```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
#include "max1270.h"

#include <cfg/os.h>
#ifdef NUTDEBUG
#include <sys/osdebug.h>
#endif

#include <stdio.h>
#include <io.h>

#include <cfg/arch.h>
#include <dev/board.h>

#include <sys/thread.h>
#include <sys/timer.h>
#include <sys/event.h>
#include <sys/heap.h>

// ADC SPI Interface
#define ADC_CS1 0x01
#define ADC_SCK 0x02
#define ADC_MOSI 0x04
#define ADC_DOUT 0x04
#define ADC_MISO 0x08
#define ADC_DIN 0x08
#define ADC_CS2 0x10

// ADC Control Register
#define ADC_PD0 0x01
#define ADC_PD1 0x02
#define ADC_BIP 0x04
#define ADC_RNG 0x08
#define ADC_SEL0 0x10
#define ADC_SEL1 0x20
#define ADC_SEL2 0x40
#define ADC_START 0x80

// Channel Selection
#define ADC_CH0 0x00<<4
#define ADC_CH1 0x01<<4
#define ADC_CH2 0x02<<4
#define ADC_CH3 0x03<<4
#define ADC_CH4 0x04<<4
#define ADC_CH5 0x05<<4
#define ADC_CH6 0x06<<4
#define ADC_CH7 0x07<<4

// Range and Polarity Selection

// CS1: OFF, CS2: OFF
#define ADC_Disel 0xE9
```

```

// CS1: ON, CS2: OFF
#define ADC_Sel_CS1 0xE8

// CS1: OFF, CS2: ON
#define ADC_Sel_CS2 0xc9

#define waitForTransmission() while ( ! ( SPSR & ( 1 << SPIF ) ) )

/*!
 * \addtogroup xgMAX1270
 */
/*@{*/
unsigned char SPITransmitting;
void delay_us(unsigned int microseconds)
{
    if (microseconds == 0)
        return;
    __asm__ volatile (
        "1: push r22" "\n\t"
        " ldi r22, 4" "\n\t"
        "2: dec r22" "\n\t"
        " brne 2b" "\n\t"
        " pop r22" "\n\t"
        " sbiw %0, 1" "\n\t"
        " brne 1b"
        : "=w" ( microseconds )
        : "0" ( microseconds )
    );
}

void delay_ms(unsigned int time_ms)
{
    if (time_ms == 0)
        return;
    __asm__ volatile (
        "1: push r22" "\n\t"
        " ldi r22, 84" "\n\t"
        "2: push r23" "\n\t"
        " ldi r23, 77" "\n\t"
        "3: dec r23" "\n\t"
        " brne 3b" "\n\t"
        " pop r23" "\n\t"
        " dec r22" "\n\t"
        " brne 2b" "\n\t"
        " pop r22" "\n\t"
        " sbiw %0, 1" "\n\t"
        " brne 1b"
        : "=w" ( time_ms )
        : "0" ( time_ms )
    );
}

```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
void Port_Init(void)
{
    PORTB = ADC_Disel;
    DDRB = 0x37;
}

// SPI initialisation
// clock rate: 921599hz
void SPI_Init(void)
{
    //SPCR = 0x0D; //setup SPI
    SPCR = (1<<SPE) | (1<<MSTR) | (1<<SPR0); // | (1<<SPR1)
    SPSR = 0x00; //setup SPI
}

/*
** SpiReadDataReg() gets the last byte from the SPI register
** without sending out any clock signals. It could be used
** to read the received last byte.
*/
void SpiWriteDataReg(unsigned char byte)
{
    SPDR = byte;
}

unsigned char SpiReadDataReg(void)
{
    return SPDR;
}

// Transmit a byte to ATmega128
void SPITransmit( unsigned char data )
{
    if ( SPITransmitting ) // prevent false SPIF clears from
        waitForTransmission(); // hanging the wait loop
    SPDR = data; // start transmission of data
    SPITransmitting = 1; // flag transmission is in progress
}

// Initiate an exchange of data with ATmega128
// by transmitting a byte
unsigned char SPIReceive( unsigned char data )
// data is often a junk byte
{
    if (SPITransmitting)
        waitForTransmission();
    // #define in SPI.h
    delay_us( 3 ); // give the ATmega128 time to prepare return data
    SPDR = data; // start bidirectional transfer
    waitForTransmission(); // #define in SPI.h
    // Reading SPCR and SPDR clears SPIF, so we will use this flag
    // to indicate that this does not mean we are now transmitting.
}
```

```

    SPITransmitting = 0;
    return SPDR;
}

void Init_ADC(unsigned char start, unsigned char channel, unsigned
    char rang_polar, unsigned char pw_clk)
{
    unsigned char tmp;
    tmp=start | channel | rang_polar | pw_clk;
    SPITransmit(tmp);
}

unsigned int Read_ADC(unsigned char num, unsigned char channel,
    unsigned char rang_polar)
{
    unsigned int result=0;
    switch (num)
    {
        case 0:
            PORTB = ADC_Sel_CS1;
            break;
        case 1:
            PORTB = ADC_Sel_CS2;
            break;
        default:;
    }
    Init_ADC(ADC_START, channel<<4, rang_polar, ADC_NORMP_EXTCLK);
    result=SPIReceive(0);
    result=(result<<9) + (SPIReceive(0)<<1);
    result+= (SPIReceive(0)>>7) & 0x01;
    SPIReceive(0);
    PORTB = ADC_Disel;
    return result;
}
/*@}*/

```

E.4 MATLAB Code

Code E.4: MATLAB M-code (adc2pc.m) for reading and plotting.

```

clear
echotcpip('on',100);
t = tcpip('192.168.0.170',100);
fopen(t);
t
fscanf(t)
s = urlread('http://192.168.0.170/cgi-bin/adc');
fclose(t);
echotcpip('off');

```

APPENDIX E. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

```
A = sscanf(s, '%x');
for i = 1:4000
    for k = 1:2
        a(k,i) = 5*A(4*(i-1)+k)/4095;
    end
    for k = 3:4
        a(k,i)=A(4*(i-1)+k);
        if a(k,i)>=2048
            a(k,i)=-(4095-a(k,i));
        end
        a(k,i) = 5*a(k,i)/2047;
    end
end
t = 0.0007:0.0007:2.8;
subplot(4,1,1);
plot(t,a(1,:));
subplot(4,1,2);
plot(t,a(2,:));
subplot(4,1,3);
plot(t,a(3,:));
subplot(4,1,4);
plot(t,a(4,:));
```

E.5 Default ROM Program

Code E.5: urom.c created by crurom 1.2.2.

```
/* This file is automatically created by crurom 1.2.2 */
#include <fs/uromfs.h>
/* File entry 1: index.html */
prog_char file1data[] = {
0x3c,0x68,0x74,0x6d,0x6c,0x3e,0x0d,0x0a,0x3c,0x68,0x65,0x61,0x64,0x3e,
0x0d,0x0a,
0x3c,0x2f,0x68,0x65,0x61,0x64,0x3e,0x0d,0x0a,0x3c,0x62,0x6f,0x64,0x79,
0x3e,0x0d,
0x0a,0x0d,0x0a,0x3c,0x68,0x31,0x3e,0x57,0x65,0x6c,0x63,0x6f,0x6d,0x65,
0x20,0x74,
0x6f,0x20,0x45,0x74,0x68,0x65,0x72,0x6e,0x75,0x74,0x20,0x48,0x54,0x54,
0x50,0x3c,
0x2f,0x68,0x31,0x3e,0x0d,0x0a,0x0d,0x0a,0x3c,0x68,0x32,0x3e,0x3c,0x2f,
0x68,0x32,
0x3e,0x0d,0x0a,0x0d,0x0a,0x3c,0x2f,0x62,0x6f,0x64,0x79,0x3e,0x0d,0x0a,
0x3c,0x2f,
0x68,0x74,0x6d,0x6c,0x3e,0x0d,0x0a,
};
prog_char file1name[] = "index.html";
static ROMENTRY file1entry = { 0, (prog_char *)file1name, 103,
    (prog_char *)file1data };
ROMENTRY *romEntryList = &file1entry;
```

E.6 Compiler Makefile

Code E.6: Makefile for compiling the codes.

```

# Copyright (C) 2001-2006 by egnite Software GmbH.
# All rights reserved. http://www.ethernut.de/
# $Log: Makefile,v $
# 2007/08/30, ADCLIB for MAX1270 added by Ashkbiz Danehkar
# Revision 1.7 2006/07/21 09:13:58 haraldkipp
PROJ = httpserv
ADCLIB = max1270.c
WEBDIR = sample
WEBFILE= urom.c

include ../Makedefs

SRCS = $(PROJ).c $(WEBFILE) $(ADCLIB)
OBJS = $(SRCS:.c=.o)
#MODS = $(MODDIR)/dev/lanc111.o
LIBS = $(LIBDIR)/nutinit.o $(MODS) -lnutpro -lnutos -lnutarch
      -lnutdev -lnutarch -lnutnet -lnutfs -lnutcrt
TARG = $(PROJ).hex

ifneq (, $(findstring h8300, $(ARCH)))
# Libraries specific for H8 port
LIBS += -lnutentry -lc -lgcc
endif

all: $(OBJS) $(TARG) $(ITARG) $(DTARG)

$(WEBFILE): $(WEBDIR)/index.html
    $(CRUROM) -r -o$(WEBFILE) $(WEBDIR)

include ../Makerules

clean:
    -rm -f $(OBJS)
    -rm -f $(TARG) $(ITARG) $(DTARG)
    -rm -f $(PROJ).eep
    -rm -f $(PROJ).obj
    -rm -f $(PROJ).map
    -rm -f $(SRCS:.c=.lst)
    -rm -f $(SRCS:.c=.bak)
    -rm -f $(SRCS:.c=.i)
    -rm -f $(WEBFILE)

```
